

RURITAGE

Heritage for Rural Regeneration

Canvas Business Models - presenting the tailored solutions for the Replicators Assessment Report

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2. Background Information

Table 1: technical information

Project Full title		Canvas Business Models - presenting the tailored solutions for the Replicators Assessment Report	
Project Acronym		RURITAGE	
Grant Agreement No.		776465	
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Work Package Title		Co-developing and co-implementing heritage-led rural regeneration plans in Replicators	
Responsible		Task 3.2 Savonia UAS	
Author(s)		Eskelinen T, Auvinen H, Saarela A-M, Savonia UAS	
Contributor(s)			
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Table 2: Abbreviations.

D	Deliverable
WP	Work Package
M	Month
RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RM/RMs	Role Model/Role Models
R/Rs	Replicator/Replicators
Canvas	Business model Canvas
CNH	Cultural and natural heritage
INTO	INTO innovation tool at into.savonia.fi
MCDS	Multi-criteria decision support
KFP	Knowledge facilitator partner

3. Summary / Abstract

This report describes Model Business Canvases presenting the tailored solutions for all Replicators. The framework was designed to suit the needs of CNH. This report includes the CNH Canvas/solution for each R, along with the description of the methodology and process and guide used to develop them.

The business model processes were organized in six Replicators during 5-11/2019. A guideline was elaborated to guide and support the process (Annex I). A training on business models was given to the Rs at Crete in May, 2019, followed by videomeetings and demo-processes to design business model workshops. Model actions as well as a state of the art of Replicators at different dimensions, and a deep analysis and validation of Rs' needs were starting points for the business model work. The business model process was designed to build business model canvases on the Model actions of cultural and natural heritage.

Task 3.2 aims at developing replicable and up-scalable participative business models for the solutions implemented within the heritage led rural regeneration plans in Rs. To this aim, a business model process and the INTO business model analysis tool, which was developed in Savonia UAS, was used and applied. Business model process includes context and participant definition, idea generation with interviews, brainstorming and questionnaires, multicriteria idea evaluation with fast visual methods, core index portfolio analysis of results, and a workshop to discuss the results and decide actions on implementation. The workshops were run within the RHHs of the Replicator and are included in the activities to be developed in Task 3.5. The INTO tool will enable participants to be involved in and committed to the process from the beginning, allowing the development of new business models, new service concepts or products (i.e. process development and development of offerings, and development of marketing, sales, organization, or business strategy), better customer service or internal processes. A special CNH Canvas framework was designed to be used and applied during the Business model process to develop tailored solutions for different actions in the 6 Rs and provide specific recommendation to replicate such solution in a viable way from an economic point of view. The INTO tool was successfully used for the multicriteria evaluation of CNH canvases in all Replicators. It provided quantitative data on the process, such as idea lists, comments on ideas, numbers of evaluations on ideas, and core index, which was used to prioritize and select best ideas for each business model. Local participants contribution was quite remarkable: 584 ideas were evaluated online by 132 evaluators with over 15000 multicriteria evaluations on ideas, showing great interest, commitment and participation. The prioritization in the CNH canvases reflects the evaluations against the chosen criteria: environmental, social, economical value, and feasibility and thus produce value added in the context of rural regeneration. The CNH Canvas framework proved to be useful and successful tool to identify essential elements of business model on model actions which are aimed to be replicable solutions in the regions. The feedback from the Replicators was good.

Further discussion and development and testing of the business models will be needed on the value proposition, needs and opportunities, key activities, key resources, financing model etc.. The work done, the CNH canvases and prioritization of ideas gives good starting point for further development. The business model process and workshops provided good opportunities for co-creation and learning.

4. Introduction

This report reflects the work done in applying business model process and CNH Canvas creation around Model actions in six Ruritage Replicators.

The report describes Business Model Canvases presenting the tailored solutions for all Replicators. The framework was designed to suit the needs of Cultural and Natural Heritage (CNH).

The report includes the completed Canvas/solution for each R, along with the description of the methodology and process and guide used to develop them. The tailored CNH Canvas framework was designed to be used and applied during the Business model process to develop tailored solutions for different actions in the 6 Rs and provide specific recommendation to replicate such solution in a viable way from an economic point of view.

Task 3.2 aims at developing replicable and up-scalable participative business models for the solutions implemented within the heritage led rural regeneration plans in Rs. To this aim, a business model process and the INTO business model analysis tool, which was developed in Savonia UAS, was used and applied.

During RURITAGE the model actions/best practices (Del 1.1, TEC) identified in the Role Models, and discussed in the Participatory Workshop, forms the backdrop for the innovative business modelling process. Participating stakeholders have been identified during the first months of the project following specific guidelines developed by project partners (Del 2.1). The baseline study of the Replicators acts as a starting point (Del 1.4 CARTIF), whilst the Business Models are evaluated by establishing value-based criteria connected to Del. 4.1 (CARTIF).

To guide the business modelling process, the following supports were available:

- An innovative Business Model Canvas for CNH has been developed and pre-tested to support the first steps towards heritage-led regeneration plans, boosting co-creation, prioritising and co-ordination of actions. Further feedback will be collected to learn from the BM processes in each R.
- A detailed Guide is provided on how to use this Business Model Canvas to facilitate the strategy development.
- The Business Modelling process is complemented by the INTO tool – an online platform for making complex decision making faster and more efficient, involving different stakeholders and providing a transparent process. This tool is guided by Savonia UAS, and is tailored to the situation of each Replicator.
- A training workshop was held for Replicators in Crete in May, 2019, along with face-to-face meetings with each Replicator, to explain the process involved and to demonstrate the use of the INTO Tool (into.savonia.fi) as a co-creation process to build actions on business models and investment strategy.

Business model process includes context and participant definition, idea generation with interviews, brainstorming and questionnaires, multicriteria idea evaluation with fast visual methods, core index portfolio analysis of results and a workshop to discuss the results and decide actions on implementation. The Business model workshops were run within the RHHs of the Replicator and are included in the activities to be developed in Task 3.5. The tool enables participants to be involved in and committed to the process from the beginning, allowing the development of new business models, new service concepts or products (i.e. process development and development of offerings, and development of marketing, sales, organization, or business strategy), better customer service or internal processes.

- Support will be provided to prepare for the Business Model Workshop to be held in each RHH. Business model process and workshop was supported by between 2-4 bilateral video meetings between Savonia

and the Replicators.

- Further assistance, through a review and feedback process, will be provided with the tailored Business Model solutions for each Replicator that can be developed in a viable way from a financial and economic perspective.

The Business models process is guided by Savonia UAS (leading task 3.2) and WestBIC, and supported by CE, CARTIF, UNIBO and ICLEI.

The guideline, attached at the end of this report, for the modelling includes detailed instructions on the approach, process, as well as description of the tailored CNH Canvas.

4.1 5 Steps Towards Business Models and Investment Strategy

The development process is a creative service design process including both divergent (Idea Development/ Model Actions) and convergent phases (evaluation and decision analysis produces prioritized list of actions). In the case of Business Modelling for Replicators in the RURITAGE project, the backdrop is the Model Actions selected from the Role Models that have potential for replication and tailoring for implementation in Replicator regions. This leads to the following 5 steps:

4 Decision analysis with core value

Gives us a prioritized list of actions to support the BM and investment strategy creation. Results will be presented as a draft CNH Canvas, and as a prioritized list of actions with development comments and commitments (who will take lead for further actions)

Savonia Core Value calculation

Savonia Business Model Canvas

#	Scenarios	Idea name	Description
1	1771	Cooperation	Not active producer organisations should be brought into a Producer organizations should be cooperate with local gover
2	1771	Create a network of local farmers	Main farmers aware of the importance of making network
3	1771	Create children board	Set up board with local primary school children that will log
4	1771	create public-private partnerships	create PPP
5	1771	Customer wants to see excellent views landscape	Customer wants to see excellent views and take photograph
6	1771	Statistics	Statistics

Discussion on results & Action plan BM and investment strategy

5

Expected results:

- 1) CNH Canvas
- 2) Prioritized and improved list of model actions

www.savonia.fi

Figures 1a and 1b. CNH Canvas creation and Evaluation of model actions with INTO tool. Business models and investment strategy process at Ruritage. Adapted from Kajanus et al. (2014¹ and 2019², Eskelinen et al., 2017³ and RURITAGE Project Plan.

Overview of the Steps

- Step 1 should already be completed as part of the Participatory Workshop, which includes a shortlisting for the proposed Model Actions, stakeholder identification and engagement
- Step 2 is the core Business Canvas completion as part of the workshop, which is organised according to the instruction in Section 3 and also using the Guide in Annex I.
- Using the online INTO tool, <https://into.savonia.fi> Steps 3.1 and 3.2 involves the evaluation of the Actions so that they can be agreed and prioritised, using a range of selected criteria. This is further explained at the end of Annex I Guide.
- Steps 4 & 5, involves decision analysis and discussion of the results as a prioritisation exercise with the input/feedback from the stakeholders at the workshop using the agreed evaluation criteria. Portfolio analysis occupies core index to calculate the results, and to put the Model Actions into a prioritized list (according to Kajanus et al., 2014). **The results will be organised within the CNH Canvas framework.**

¹ Kajanus, Iire, Eskelinen, Heinonen, Hansen: Business model design: new tools for business systems innovation. Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research 08/2014; 29(6). DOI:10.1080/02827581.2014.949301.

² Kajanus M, et al., What can we learn from business models in the European forest sector: Exploring the key elements of new business model designs Forest Policy and Economics. Volume 99, February 2019, Pages 145-156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2018.04.005>

³ Eskelinen, T., Räsänen, T., Santti, U., Happonen, A., & Kajanus, M. 2017. Designing a Business Model for Environmental Monitoring Services Using Fast MCDS Innovation Support Tools. Technology Innovation Management Review, 7(11): 36-46. <http://doi.org/10.22215/timreview/1119>

4.2 Timeline

The timeline for undertaking the Local Business Models Workshop is identified below, as part of the process of developing heritage-led regeneration plans. The final timeline was extended, by the end of December, 2019.

Timeline and Project input

Figure 2: Timeline and Project Inputs for the development of Rural Regeneration Plans for RURITAGE Replicators

To facilitate this timeline, the Training Workshop for Rs on Business Models took place in Crete at the end of May, along with face-to-face discussions with Savonia to guide the process for the Local Business Model Workshops.

The guidance documents for organising and running the Workshop and the tools to be used were circulated in advance so that the business model workshops were be organized by every local Hub, guided by Savonia, with follow-up support provided according to the timeline above.

5. Business Model Canvases presenting the tailored solutions for the Replicators

5.1 Pilgrimage (R1): Arge Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken

5.1.1 Overall Description

The Karavanke/Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark is a crossborder Geopark between Austria and Slovenia, connected and divided by the mountain range with the same name. A total of 14 municipalities from Austria (9) and Slovenia (5) form the area of the Geopark Karavanke, 1067 km² large with a population of approximately 53.000. The Karavanke/Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark extends between two 2,000-metre-high Alpine peaks: the Petzen/Mt. Peca and the Koschuta Massif. It is characterized by rich geological diversity between the Alps and the Dinarides. Exceptional geological structure was the basis for the development of mine, iron (work) and coal mine industry. Rich cultural and natural heritage offer today numerous opportunities for active leisure time.

5.1.2 Process description

- Selection of the 5 Model Actions (at the Participatory workshop, 12. 07. 2019)
- Business Model Workshop implementation – 7. 10. 2019 (collection of ideas)
- Evaluation – after Business Model Workshop (online)

5.1.3 Goal of the process

At the Participatory workshop (12. 07. 2019), we defined 5 model actions for which we believe that can contribute to the successful development of our region. The business model workshop goal was to bring these model actions “alive”. We were discuss about each individual model action and worked in detail when, what to do and who will be involved in the model action activities.

5.1.4 List of selected model actions for the BM process

Table 3. Model actions selected.

1.6	Digitalisation of the pilgrimage through websites, gis maps, apps, ...
2.3	Create a set of guided tours or organized travels tailored for different target groups
3.3	Definition of marketing and communication strategies for the products
8.1	Creation of a set of tourist packs composed by food, art and naturalistic related activities

5.1.5 Organisation of the workshop

Business model workshop took place on the 7th of October, in Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken Rural Heritage Hub (Tichoja 15, Municipality of Sittersdorf). Business model workshop was divided into:

- Presentation of selected Model Actions 1.6, 2.3, 3.3, and 8.1.
- Presentation of the CNH Canvas
- Collection of new ideas
- Presentation and explanation of the evaluation questionnaire
- Homework - on-line evaluation with the INTO Tool

5.1.6 Results (CNH Canvases), next steps, recommendations (to replicate the solutions), feedback

- 4 Canvases were drafted in the workshop and evaluated with the INTO tool

Table4. Draft CNH Canvas Create a set of guided tours or organized travels for different target groups

INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		VALUE PROPOSITION	CREATING VALUE	
<p>Key Resources</p> <p>Cultural resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Archaeological museum - Archaeological excavations (Hemmaberg) <p>Natural resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Landscape - Protected areas 	<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TVS (development agency) - Geopark Karavanke / Karawanken - Accomodation partners - ARGE Pilgern Kärnten - Geschichtsverein - Archaeological Museum - Restaurations (Hemmastüberl) - Church - Media - Local authorities (14 municipalities) 	<p>Needs & Opportunities</p> <p>Create a set of guided tours or organized travels tailored for different target groups</p> <p>We could try to include new guided tour into “Active Card Programm”, for example: guided tour <u>“Pilgrimage for beginners”</u>. Information:</p> <p>Duration: cca. 6 h</p> <p>Way: St. Philippen RHH - Hemmaberg</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hemmastüberl - - Archaeological Museum - - Jaunstein - Kristendorf - <p>St. Philippen RHH</p> <p>When?</p> <p>In april, maj, september, october (not to hot!)</p> <p>Idea: At the end in our RHH participants receive award “Urkunde für erste Pilgerreise”</p>	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Get in touch with key partners in the region - Sit together with key partners - Development the activity timeline - Creation of guided tours - Implementation - Promotional activities 	<p>Beneficiaries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TVS - 14 municipalities - 2 countries - Karavanke / Karawanken - UNESCO Global Geopark - Local stores / markets - Local inhabitants - Customers - Tourists - Accomodation partners - Transfer companies - Museums - Activities providers - Restaurants
<p>Governance</p> <p>Karavanke / Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark is crossborder geopark between Slovenia and Austria and it covers 14 municipalities. We are the manager of the UNESCO recognized area. Karavanke / Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark already implements some guided tours regularly (April-Oktober), like: Hike “Sunrise in the Geopark”, Petzen panoramic circular hike, Family adventure hike, Culturally historical cross-border hike, Two wheels – two countries – a borderless cycle experience, “On the Border“ hike, ...). Some tours are already included into “Active Card Programm” (Tourismusregion Klopeiner See - Südkärnten GmbH). This is regional touristic card system which is offered as an weekly guided program for free to all tourists of the Tourist region of Klopeinersee - South Carinthia (overnights per year: ~ 800.000). Because Karavanke / Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark has experiences with guided tours and has also qualified (trained) guides, we think it is suitable to establish, coordinate and promote new guided tours.</p> <p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Karavanke/Karawanken UGG will need resources for promotional activities of guided tours. 		<p>Capturing Value</p> <p>Economic: Growth in local business (accommodations, restaurants, activity providers), increased income for locals</p> <p>Social: Building local identity, history, increase of quality of life</p> <p>Environmental: sustainable development</p>	<p>Relationships & Channels</p> <p>Newspapers, Social medias (Facebook, Tweeter), Web pages, All partners</p>	
FINANCIAL MODEL /INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

Table 5. INTO results. Prioritization by core index. A set of guided tours or organized travels for different target groups.

Savonia Business Model Canvas	
<p>Relationships and channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accommodation Partners/activity providers • Newspapers • Social medias • Web pages 	<p>Key partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accomodation partners • Archaeological Museum • ARGE Pilgerm Kärnten • Church • Geopark Karawanken • Geschichtsverein • Local authorities • Restaurants in the area along the route • Tourismusverband Südkärnten (TVS) • Firma Gastfreund
<p>Key resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Archaeological Pilgrimage Museum • Archeological excavations (Hemmaberg) • Hemmapilgerweg • Landscape • Protected area (Landschaftsschutzgebiet) 	<p>Governance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geopark Karawanke • Tourismusverband Südkärnten
<p>Needs and opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a set of guided tours or organized travels tailored for different target groups 	<p>Creating value: key activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of guided tours • Development of the activity timeline • Extend the season (spring and autumn) • Get in touch with key partners and sit together with them • Promotional activities at the international fairs, online marketing
<p>Creating value: beneficiaries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geopark area - 14 municipalities - 2 countries • Local inhabitants • Local stores/markets/restaurants • Museums • Tourismusverband Südkärnten • Tourists/visitors • Transfer companies (Taxi, buscompanies) 	<p>Capturing value</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic: Growth in local business (accommodations, restaurants, activity providers) • Economic: Increase income for locals • Environmental: Sustainable development • Social: Building local identity and history • Social: Increase of quality of life

Table 6. Draft CNH Canvas on Digitalization of the pilgrimage through websites, GIS maps, apps.

INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		VALUE PROPOSITION	CREATING VALUE	
Key Resources	Key Partners	Needs & Opportunities	Key Activities	Beneficiaries
Existing digital material (ARGE Pilgern Kärnten)	TVS - Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken - Accomodation partners - ARGE Pilgern Kärnten - External expert - Activity providers - RRA Koroška	Digitalization of the pilgrimage through websites, GIS maps, apps, ... <i>Establishment of "live" mobile application, which will also include all touristic offers and informed each person with the downloaded app about the events along pilgrimage route and entire Geopark area</i>	- Get in touch with key partners in the region - Sit together with key partners - Finding suitable external expert - Development the activity timeline - Implementation - Promotional activities	- 14 municipalities - 2 countries - Karavanke / Karawanken - UNESCO Global Geopark - Local inhabitants - Tourists - TVS (tourism agency) - Activity providers
Governance			Relationships & Channels	
Karavanke/Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark is crossborder geopark between Slovenia and Austria and it covers 14 municipalities. We are the manager of the UNESCO recognized area that is why Karavanke / Karawanken UNESCO Globals Geopark is best suited to keep a broad overview of the area and be the coordinator of the mobile application development, done by an external expert.			Social medias (Facebook, Tweeter)	
Cost Structure		Capturing Value		
Within RURITAGE Project we have: <u>20.000</u> € for the Digitalization of the pilgrimage - integration of the digitalized route within the existing website, development of GIS maps and mobile application		Economic: Growth in local business, increased income for locals Social: Building local identity, history, increase of quality of life, bringing people together across municipalities and countries Environmental: Sustainable development Other: The area will be more visible, additional value for the touristic offer		
FINANCIAL MODEL /INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

Table 7. INTO results. Prioritization of ideas by core index. Digitalization of the pilgrimage through websites, GIS maps, apps.

Savonia Business Model Canvas	
<p>Relationships and channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media • Newspapers 	<p>Key partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 14 Municipalities • ARGE Pilgerm Kärnten • External Expert • Geopark Karawanken • RRA Koroška (Tourismusverband für Koroška) • Tourismusverband Südkärnten (TVS)
<p>Key resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing digital material (ARGE Pilgerm) • Feratel - system • Geopuls - system 	<p>Governance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geopark Karawanken
<p>Needs and opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digitalization of the pilgrimage route through websites, GIS maps, Apps, ... 	<p>Creating value: key activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finding suitable external expert • Get in touch and working with key partners • Implementation activity • Promotional activities • Promotional activities
<p>Creating value: beneficiaries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 14 municipalities of the Geopark Karawanken • Accommodation providers • Tourists (Pilgrims, Hikers, Climbers, Mountaintalkers, ...) • TVS 	<p>Cost structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Already financially settled
<p>Capturing value</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic • Environmental • Others • Social 	

Table 8. INTO results. Prioritization of ideas by core index. Creation of a set of tourist packs composed by food, art and naturalistic related act.

Savonia Business Model Canvas	
<p>Relationships and channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newspapers Local • Social media Facebook • Social media Instagram • Social media Twitter 	<p>Key partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accomodation providers Created packages are an additional value • Local food and drink producers • Museums Created packages are an additional value • RRA Koroška • Tourismusverband Südkärnten (TVS)
<p>Key resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Culture Museums • Existing festivals Faranifest • Local food and drink The Geopark area has a rich potential in local food (Buckwheat products • Natural resources - landscape 	<p>Governance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KaravanteKarawanken UNESCO Global Geopark Karawanken is the manager of the UNESCO recognized area
<p>Needs and opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of a set of tourist packs composed by food 	<p>Creating value: key activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of packages • Get in touch with key partners and working with them Get in touch with various local food producers • Promotional activities As soon as the packages will be created
<p>Creating value: beneficiaries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accomodation providers • Geopark area - 14 municipalities - 2 countries KaravanteKarawanken UNESCO Global Geopark is crossborder Geopark between Austria and Slovenia. Both countries will have benefits with the establishment of the packages • Local food and drink producers • Local food and drink producers will have the opportunity to „increase income • Museums • Touristsvisitors New tourism opportunities 	<p>Cost structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resources for the creation and promotion of the packages From Geopark KaravanteKarawanken
<p>Capturing value</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic: Growth in local business The created packages will support economy within local rural communities • Economic: Increase income for locals New created packages will strengthen the connection with local producers • Environmental: Through packages we will support sustainable development of the region • Social: Building local identity and history inhabitants get more aware of their own rich cultural and natural heritage • Social: Increase the quality of life Secure jobs cause social peace 	

Table 9. Draft CNH Canvas on Creation of a set of tourist packs composed by food, art and naturalistic related act.

INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		VALUE PROPOSITION	CREATING VALUE	
<p>Key Resources</p> <p>Cultural resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local food, local wine - Museums - Archaeological excavations - Mines <p>Natural resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Landscape - Caves - Protected areas - Waterfalls 	<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TVS (development agency) - RRA Koroška - Geopark Karavanke / Karawanken - Accommodation partners - Archaeological Museum - Restorations - Media - Local authorities (14 municipalities) - Local food and wine producers (Had'n, Salami, Sittersdorfer wine) - Arlitscherhof - Kulturni dom Pliberk / Bleiburg - Koroški pokrajinski muzej - Medias 	<p>Needs & Opportunities</p> <p>Creation of a set of tourist packs composed by food, art and naturalistic related activities</p>	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Get in touch with key partners in the region - Sit together with key partners - Development the activity timeline - Creation of packages - Implementation - Promotional activities 	<p>Beneficiaries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TVS - 14 municipalities - 2 countries - Karavanke / Karawanken - UNESCO Global Geopark - Local stores / markets - Local inhabitants - Customers - Tourists - Accomodation partners - Transfer companies - Museums - Activities providers - Restaurants - Local food producers
<p>Governance</p> <p>Karavanke / Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark is crossborder geopark between Slovenia and Austria and it covers 14 municipalities. We are the manager of the UNESCO recognized area that is why Karavanke / Karawanken UNESCO Globals Geopark is best suited to kepp a broad overview of the area and be the coordinator of tourist packages development.</p>			<p>Relationships & Channels</p> <p>Newspapers, Social medias (Facebook, Tweeter), Web pages, All partners</p>	
<p>Cost Structure</p> <p>- Karavanke/Karawanken UGG will need resources for creation and promotional activities of created packages.</p>		<p>Capturing Value</p> <p>Economic: Growth in local business (accommodations, restaurants, activity providers), increased income for locals.</p> <p>Social: Building local identity, history, increase of quality of life</p> <p>Environmental: Sustainable development</p>		
<p>FINANCIAL MODEL /INVESTMENT STRATEGY</p>				

Table 10. Draft CNH Canvas on Definition of marketing and communication strategies for the product

INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		VALUE PROPOSITION	CREATING VALUE	
<p>Key Resources</p> <p>Cultural resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local food - Local wine - Had'n (Buckwheat) - Salami - Local producers 	<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "Had'n" (Buckwheat) association - Salami association - Sittersdorfer Wine - Organic farmers (Tomažej, ...) - Kotschnig farm - Bauernbund (farmers organization) - Arlitscherhof - Local Food producers 	<p>Needs & Opportunities</p> <p>Definition of marketing and communication strategies for the products</p>	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Get in touch with Magma UGG where GEOfood brand was established - Get in touch with key partners (food and wine producers) in the region - Sit together with key partners - Development the activity timeline - GEOfood brand implementation ("bringing" the GEOfood brand in our region) - Event for GEOfood presentation - Promotional activities <p>Relationships & Channels</p> <p>Newspapers, Social medias (Facebook, Tweeter), Web pages, All partners, GEOfood brand</p>	<p>Beneficiaries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local food/wine producers - 14 municipalities - 2 countries - Karavanke / Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark - Local stores/markets - Local inhabitants - Customers - Tourists
<p>Governance</p> <p>Karavanke/Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark is crossborder geopark between Slovenia and Austria and it covers 14 municipalities. We are the manager of the UNESCO recognized area. Within UNESCO Geoparks GEOfood brand already exists. It is international brand, really well recognized. It is brand for local food in UNESCO Global Geoparks territories and it is registered by Magma UNESCO Global Geopark. That is why Karavanke/Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark is suitable to coordinate GEOfood brand within Its area.</p>				
<p>Cost Structure</p> <p>Within RURITAGE Project we have: <u>10.000 €</u> for food branding creation and marketing <u>10.000 €</u> for activities related with SIA Food (organization of events related with local food production, development of online training courses for local producers)</p>		<p>Capturing Value</p> <p>Economic: Growth in local business, increased income for locals Social: Building local identity, history, increase of quality of life Environmental: sustainable development</p>		
FINANCIAL MODEL /INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

Table 11. INTO results. Prioritization of ideas by core index. Definition of marketing and communication strategies for the product.

Savonia Business Model Canvas	
<p>Relationships and channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newspapers Presentation of the brand in local newspapers • Social medias Facebook Twitter Instagram 	<p>Key partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local food producers Geopark area has several local producers • Local Restaurants The GEOfood restaurants will serve GEOfood dishes – from the Geopark- Region
<p>Key resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local food and drink Geopark area has a rich potential in local food (Buckwheat products Salami Karavanienfisch Honey...) and drink (Sittersdorfer wine apple cider (Most) ...) 	<p>Governance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Karvanien/Karavanien UNESCO Global Geopark Karavanien/Karavanien UNESCO Global Geopark is a crossborder geopark between Slovenia and Austria and it covers 14 municipalities. We are the manager of the UNESCO recognized area. Within UNESCO Geoparks GEOfood brand already exists. It is an international brand really well recognized. It is a brand for local food in UNESCO Global Geoparks territories and it is registered by Magma UNESCO Global Geopark. That is why Karavanien/Karavanien UNESCO Global Geopark is suitable to coordinate GEOfood brand within its area
<p>Needs and opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of marketing and communication strategies for the products. When „bringing the already existing GEOfood brand into the Geopark area marketing and communication strategies are necessary 	<p>Creating value: key activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event for GEOfood presentation Official event for the presentation of the GEOfood products in our region is necessary • GEOfood implementation Bringing GEOfood brand in our region • Get in touch and working with Key partners Get in touch with local food and drink producers who are interested to receive the GEOfood brand • Get in touch with Magma UNESCO Global Geopark GEOfood brand is already existing (international) food brand registered by Magma UNESCO Global Geopark • Promotional activities at international fairs online marketing Promotional activities for the GEOfood products at the international level
<p>Creating value: beneficiaries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geopark area - 14 municipalities - 2 countries Karavanien/Karavanien UNESCO Global Geopark between Austria and Slovenia. Both countries will have benefits with the establishment of the GEOfood brand • Local food and drink producers local restaurants Local food and drink producers will have the opportunity to get international GEOfood brand and the promotion at an international level • Local inhabitants GEOfood brand aims to strengthen the connection with local producers restaurants and other businesses to create synergies and economic opportunities • Local stores/markets GEOfood brand aims to strengthen the connection with local producers restaurants and other businesses to create synergies and economic opportunities • Tourists/visitors New tourism opportunities will connect visitors with the authentic feeling of an UNESCO Global Geopark through local food millenary traditions in order to provide them with authentic experiences 	<p>Cost structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Branding and marketing costs • SIA Food related activities
<p>Capturing value</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic Growth in local business • Economic Increase income for locals 	

- Using the CNH Canvas within the workshop helped to be more efficient – not just the participants could sort their ideas and comments, also for us in our future work, when we look at each single canvas we clearly can check for example our key partners, or the resources and how they are connected with each other.
- In case we must describe our Model Actions to people who are not familiar with the whole project we can do this within using the canvas.
- The idea of developing ideas within this canvas was not completely new to the participants – those who work on projects were already working in frames like that.
- Unfortunately we have no feedback (from the evaluators) about the evaluation that was made later, online by each participant. 13 stakeholders made on-line evaluation (we sent invitation also to stakeholders, who could not attend the Business model workshop event, but are familiar with the RURITAGE project and actions we want to implement in the frame of the project).
- For us the CNH Canvas helped extremely, we could show directly the participants the connections between each point.
- Additionally it was useful because we were actually lead through the meeting – working point by point, not missing an important detail.
- The results of the evaluation process (Savonia) were interesting for us.
- It fits very well into our local process and it will help us to explain other people what actions we are planning to implement and how we will do that in detail.

Figures 3-5: The Business model workshop gathered 8 participants who brainstormed four action canvases. INTO evaluation took place in 3 weeks after the workshop.

5.2 Local Food (R2): Magma UNESCO Global Geopark

The key for tourism growth and for strengthening the cultural and geological values in Magma UNESCO Global Geopark

Magma UNESCO Global Geopark is a geographic area with a geology that has a major international importance, recognized by UNESCO, and where sustainable development plays an important role. Magma geopark is in a network of 140 UNESCO Global Geoparks in 40 different countries on 5 continents and their representatives meet regularly. Although the background for a geopark is geology, really, it's all about the people – both locals and tourists, who are willing to explore, experience and share the vast possibilities of the natural and cultural attractions in the geopark!

5.2.1 Overall Description

Magma UG is located in southwest Norway, about one hour by car or train southeast of Stavanger. The Geopark is mostly situated in Rogaland County but the eastern sector is in Vest-Agder County (Fig. 1). The Rogaland Anorthosite Province (RAP) and its metamorphic envelope provide the geological basis for Magma UG, but it covers an area of five municipalities – Eigersund, Sokndal, Lund and Bjerkreim in Rogaland County and Flekkefjord in Vest-Agder County. The four municipalities in Rogaland County also comprise the Dalane district, comprising a total administrative area of 2.329 km².

5.2.2 Process description

The business model process followed the guideline: context description, selection of model actions, drafting of three CNH canvases, workshop with discussion and INTO evaluation, reporting.

5.2.3 Goal of the process

The goal was to make CNH Canvases on three model actions selected at the participatory workshop.

5.2.4 List of selected model actions for the BM process

Table 12. Model actions selected.

RM12-1	Promote joint actions (also through PPP) to enhance heritage resources and create an internationally recognized brand.
RM4-9	Promote the tourist offer of all 5 municipalities through the design of a tourist route that specifies restaurants, hotels and shops.
RM3-1	Support local farmers and producers in innovation projects.
RM3-3	Definition of marketing and communication strategies for the products.
RM10-1	Discover and diffuse traditional storytelling and superstitions to understand the natural environment and promote the place ownership.

RM4-10	Promote the tourist offer of both municipalities through the design of a tourist route that specifies restaurants, hotels and shops.
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5.2.5 Organisation of the workshop

The workshop was organised 5th of November, 2019 with 8 participants.

5.2.6 Results (CNH Canvases), next steps, recommendations (to replicate the solutions), feedback

The participants were enthusiastic and positive. The first part of the workshop involved going through the Business Model Canvases in groups. This led to good discussions and lots of engagement. We had to stop this part after about 40 minutes, but if it was up to the participants (and us) we would have continued this instead of heading to the INTO-tool. The key takeaway is that discussions around the table is a great way of communicating needs and suggestions in a small group like this.

The participants preferred working in groups instead of working at computers individually. Three CNH Canvases were elaborated. The CNH Canvas was very useful in our workshop. It started a lot of fruitful discussions and it also gave the participants a good overview of each Role Model action selected and what is needed to activate and implement them. 3 Canvases were drafted in the workshop and evaluated with the INTO tool:

Table 13. INTO results. Prioritization of ideas by core index. RM 12-1.

Savonia Business Model Canvas	
<p>Samarbeid & kanaler</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Årlig rapportoppsummering knyttet til disse aktivitetene. • Merkearebygging via Magma Geopark • Merkearebygging via Opplev Bjerkreim • Merkearebygging via Vest-Egersund • Merkearebygging via Visit Flekkefjord • Samlinger for alle lokale samarbeidspartnere i aktivitet knyttet til RURITAGE en gang i året. • Samlinger for lokale GEOfood-produsentersamarbeidspartnere minst 1 gang pr år. 	<p>Nøkkelpartnere</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Egersund Nærings- og havn • Flekkefjord, Soknial, Lund, Bjerkreim & Egersund kommune • Fylkesmannen Rogaland • Fylkesmannen Vest-Agder • Lokale aktivitetsbydere • Lokale produsenter • Lund Næringsutvikling • Region Stavanger • Rogaland Fylkeskommune • Smabyen Flekkefjord • Bjerkreim Næringshage • Vest-Agder Fylkeskommune
<p>Nøkkelressurser</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 46 lokaliteter • Dalane Folkemuseum • Dalane Friluftsråd • Etlandskap anerkjent av UNESCO • Flekkefjord museum • FOT • Lister Friluftsråd • Lund Bygdemuseum og kulturbank 	<p>VERDIFORSLAG Behov & muligheter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Behov for samarbeidsarenaer/merke i geoparkområdet innen lokal mat (GEOfood) og reiseliv. • Vi har behov for å bygge en felles identitet innen UNESCO-området, og synliggjøre verdien av UNESCO sin anerkjennelse av området for de lokale. • Vi har behov for bedre, og tydeligere dialog/kommunikasjon mellom våre eiere, Magma og alle involverte aktører.
<p>Verdiskaping: Nøkkelaktiviteter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Få så mange lokale produsenter som mulig til å bruke GEOfood på sine produkter, for å samkjøre promoteringen av området. • Kurs for guider i alle 5 kommuner for å sikre lokal kunnskapsoverføring og god kvalitet på kumiskapen. • Lage matlapper og matlurer • Promotere og bruke Magma UNESCO Global Geopark sin logo på alle partnernes nettsider og sosiale medier. 	<p>Verdiskaping: Mottakere</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aktivitetsbydere • Hotell/overnattingssteder • Lokale butikker og markeder • Lokale produsenter • Magma Geopark • Museer • Økt publisitet • Spiessteder • Lokale innbyggere • Økt publisitet • Alle 5 kommuner • Begge fylkene
<p>Kostnader</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Et mindre årlig beløp fra lokale produsenter som ønsker å bruke GEOfood-merket. • Som koordinator av tilbudet til turister i området vil Magma trenge årlige tilskudd fra alle 5 kommuner for å dekke bruk av timer til dette arbeidet. 	

Table 14. CNH Canvas with prioritized ideas by core index. RM -12.1.

2. INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		1. VALUE PROPOSITION	3. CREATING VALUE	
Key Resources	Key Partners		Key Activities	Beneficiaries
46 localities	Flekkefjord, Sokndal, Lund, Bjerkreim, Eigersund municipalities	Create an internationally recognized brand on GEOfood Needs & Opportunities	Promoting, and using the Magma UNESCO Global Geopark brand, on all partners social medias.	Local producers
An area recognized by UNESCO	Local producers		Create food trails	Increased publicity
Lund Bygdemuseum	Local activity providers			Magma Geopark
FOT	Smaabyen Flekkefjord Eigersund Næring- og havn	We need to establish local networks related to communication between partners.	Get as many local producers as possible to use the GEOfood brand, as a unifier.	Local stores and markets
Dalane friluftsråd	Bjerkreim Næringshage		Guide courses in all 5 municipalities to ensure local knowledge transfer and quality on offer.	Accommodation (Hotels, camping, cottages etc.)
Lister friluftsråd	Lund Næringsutvikling	Local food (GEOfood) Tourism		Local inhabitants
	Region Stavanger			Museums
	Vest-Agder County Rogaland County	We need to build a joint and common identity within the UNESCO recognized area and visualize the value of this recognition locally		Activity providers
	County Governor Rogaland and Agder			Restaurants
Governance			Relationships & Channels	
			Gatherings for local GEOfood producers/stakeholders ones a year	
			Gatherings for all local participants in RURITAGE actions at least ones a year	
			Annual report connected to this action	
			Building a brand through channels:	
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opplev Bjerkreim • Visit Eigersund • Visit Flekkefjord • Webpage Magma Geopark 	
	Cost Structure			
4. FINANCIAL MODEL /INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

Table 15. INTO results. Prioritization of ideas by core index. RM 4-10.

Savonia Business Model Canvas	
<p>Samarbeid & kanaler</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nyhetsbrev fra Magma og partnere • På alle parmeres, inkludert Magmas, sosiale medier og nettsider. 	<p>Nøkkelpartnere</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • En definert kontaktperson i hver kommune. • Visit Egersund • Region Stavanger • Smaabyen Flekkefjord
<p>Nøkkelressurser</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alle lokale festivaler • Visit Egersund og Smaabyen Flekkefjord sitt allerede eksisterende nettverk • Merkevaren Magma UNESCO Global Geopark 	<p>VERDIFORSLAG Behov & muligheter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Felles digital plattform • Koordinator • Ressurser til koordinator • Godt samarbeid mellom alle lokale aktører • Ressurser til å opprette en felles kalender
<p>Verdiskaping: Nøkkelaktiviteter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opprette gode rutiner for å spille inn festivaler og arrangementer til kalenderen. • Definere hvor kalenderen skal publiseres og hvordan. • Definere hvilken digital plattform som skal brukes. 	<p>Verdiskaping: Mottakere</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alle 5 kommunene • Lokale småprodusenter (mat, håndverk) • Tettstederbyer • Lokale festivaler og markeder • Magma Geopark/UNESCO • Begge fylkene
<p>Kostnader</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Økonomisk støtte til å koordinere, oppdatere og promotere kalenderen. • Økonomisk støtte til å opprette kalender 	

Table 16. CNH Canvas with prioritized ideas by core index. RM- 4-10

2. INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		1. VALUE PROPOSITION	3. CREATING VALUE	
<p>Key Resources</p> <p>All local festivals</p> <p>The existing network of Visit Egersund and Smaabyen Flekkefjord</p> <p>The brand Magma UNESCO Global Geopark</p>	<p>Key Partners</p> <p>Smaabyen Flekkefjord</p> <p>Visit Egersund</p> <p>Region Stavanger</p>	<p>Design</p> <p>a shared calendar service for each fair of folk heritage and festivals to promote tourism.</p> <p>Needs & Opportunities</p> <p>We need a shared digital platform</p> <p>A coordinator</p> <p>Positive and efficient collaboration with all local stakeholders involved</p>	<p>Key Activities</p> <p>Establish good routines for gathering information from local festivals and events.</p>	<p>Beneficiaries</p> <p>All municipalities</p> <p>Magma Geopark/UNESCO</p> <p>Both counties</p> <p>Local festivals and markets</p> <p>Local small-scale producers (food, crafts)</p> <p>Towns/villages</p>
<p>Governance</p>		<p>Resources for a coordinator</p>	<p>Relationships & Channels Communication:</p> <p>All partners, including Magmas, social medias</p> <p>Newsletters from Magma</p>	
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial support to create the calendar. Financial support to coordinate, update and promote the calendar. 			<p>Capturing value: selling advertisements on social media</p>	
<p>4. FINANCIAL MODEL /INVESTMENT STRATEGY</p>				

Table 17. INTO results. Prioritization of ideas by core index. RM 4-9.

Savonia Business Model Canvas	
<p>Samarbeid & kanaler</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aktivitetsbydere • Smaabyen Flekketjord/Visit Flekketjord • Visit Egersund • Alle partnere, inkludert Magmas, sosiale media og nettside • Nyhetsbrev fra partnere og Magma • Opplev Bjerkreim 	<p>Nøkkelpartnere</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lokale produsenter i alle 5 kommuner. • Overnattingssteder i alle 5 kommuner. • Spisesteder i alle 5 kommuner. • Visit Egersund
<p>Nøkkelressurser</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • De mest populære og tilgjengelige lokalitetene i geopartien imen kultur, natur og historie. • GEOfoodlokal mat • Merkevaren Magma UNESCO Global Geopark • Åpne bondegårder • Infrastruktur 	<p>VERDIFORSLAG Behov & muligheter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Reason to come - reason to stay" • Mer samarbeid innen pakketering av de ulike produktene i området (overnattig, bespisning, opplevelse og aktivitet). • Mer verdiskaping ut av de lokale ressursene vi har i området.
<p>Verdiskaping: Nøkkelaktiviteter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definere en hovedrute som inkluderer spisesteder, hoteller, aktiviteter og produsenter, og som kan deles opp eller utvides etter behov og utvikling. • Inngå kontrakt med alle involverte parter. 	<p>Verdiskaping: Mottakere</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lokale spisesteder • Alle 5 kommuner • Begge fylker • Lokale aktivitetsbydere • Lokale overnattingssteder • Lokale produsenter • Magma Geopark/UNESCO
<p>Kostnader</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Koordinator vil trenge økonomiske ressurser for å opprette, koordinere og promotere disse turistrutene. 	

Table 18. Prioritization of ideas to CNH Canvas by core index. RM- 4-9.

2. INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		1. VALUE PROPOSITION	3. CREATING VALUE	
Key Resources	Key Partners	<p>Promote cultural, historical and geological tourist offer of all 5 municipalities through the design of a tourist route that specifies services restaurants, hotels, activities and producers.</p> <p>Needs & Opportunities "Reason to come – reason to stay"</p> <p>More collaboration regarding making tourist packages in the area (accommodations, restaurants, adventure and activities)</p> <p>Creating more value-based services on our local resources</p>	Key Activities	Beneficiaries
<p>The most accessible and popular localities in the geopark area related to both culture/history and geology/nature.</p> <p>GEOfood/local food</p>	<p>Hotels in each municipality</p> <p>Restaurants in each municipality</p> <p>Local producers in each municipality</p>		<p>Define one or more trails including restaurants, hotels, activities and producers</p> <p>Get all formal agreements signed</p>	<p>Local producers</p> <p>Local hotels</p> <p>Local restaurants</p> <p>Local activity providers</p> <p>All municipalities</p> <p>Magma Geopark/ UNESCO</p>
		<p>Relationships & Channels Communication: All partners, including Magma, social medias</p> <p>Smaabyen Flekkefjord</p> <p>Activity providers</p> <p>Visit Egersund</p>		
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordinator will need financial recourses to create, coordinate and promote these trails. 				
4. FINANCIAL MODEL /INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

5.3 Migration (R3): Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße Odenwald e.V.

MIGRATION

Working for CNH as a way for migrants' integration in the territory of Geo-Naturpark Bergstrasse-Odenwald (State of Hesse, Baden-Württemberg, Bavaria)

5.3.1 Overall Description

The Geopark territory represents four major geological units, which provide a record of 500 million years of Earth history. The western “Crystalline Odenwald” consists of plutonic rocks (e.g. granite, gabbro) and metamorphic schists (500 – 340 million years ago). The sandstones and mudstones of the eastern “Bunter Sandstone Odenwald” were deposited in temporary rivers and lakes (245 million years ago). The limestones of the “Muschelkalk” area were deposited in a shallow sea. The rifting of the “Upper Rhine Graben” started about 50 million years ago and is still active (consistently evidenced by earthquakes). Volcanic phases are documented in basalts, rhyolites and phonolites. Periods of weathering, erosion and deposition during the ice ages (2 million to 10.000 years ago) modified the landscape as we see it today. Geological heritage of international significance: UNESCO World Heritage Site “Messel Pit” (located in the municipality of Messel near Darmstadt functions as northern entrance gate and information centre of the Geo-Naturpark Bergstrasse-Odenwald) with unique fossils and climate archive (volcanic maar structure, 48 million years). Type locality (Locus classicus et typicus) for “Loess” in Heidelberg, Pleistocene soft rock, globally first mentioned by K. C. von Leonard (1823).

5.3.2 Process description

The business model process included preparation: one meeting at Crete and three video meetings with Savonia UAS to define the context, goals, participants, timeline and agenda for the meeting. The INTO tool was used in the idea generation to the CNH canvas before workshop, and their multicriteria evaluation after workshop. INTO results (draft Canvases) were discussed to finalize the CNH canvases.

5.3.3 Goal of the process

Goal was to elaborate three CNH Canvases. Three canvases were drafted on the model actions before the workshop.

5.3.4 List of selected model actions for the BM process

Table 19. Model actions selected.

RM7-2	provide opportunities for all ages and abilities to experience, participate and work in the arts within a predominantly rural context
RM5-2	capacity building activities: training to migrants and residents related with organic farming, arts, built heritage restoration
RM2-3	create a set of guided tours or organized travels, tailored for different targets
RM1-7	foster training and employment: school workshops and internships

RM6-2	educational programmes and guided tours, specifically tailored for migrants to make them aware of the CNH of the territory
RM3-1	support local farmers and producers in innovation projects
RM11-2	design a framework for integrated management
RM8-2	promote and support local traditional activities
RM4-5	define an action plan for the communication of the biodiversity of the area
RM7-7	collaborate with other theatres, art centres, art programmers, in the area to provide a join up cultural offer
RM9-2	develop interactive exhibitions to attract a broader audience

5.3.5 Organisation of the workshop

The workshop was organised 18 of November with 13 participants. The workshop venue was the rural Regeneration Hub Lorch. Target group was visitors of the Geopark, institutions, partners who have close contact to visitors, and municipalities. Also, UNESCO participant was present at the workshop, 1 hr was used to brainstorm ideas, and 2 hrs to evaluate them. Three INTO environments were prepared by Savonia beforehand and evaluation instructions were provided.

Agenda of the event

- Short Introduction to Ruritage, the business model workshop and the action plan
- Explanation of the three actions and pilot projects
- Active part where participants discuss and add new ideas to the CNH Canvases
- Demonstration of the INTO-Tool and the evaluation process
- Conclusion and outlook for future meetings

Figure 6. Business model workshop at Geo-N.

Figure 7. CNH Canvas brainstorming at Geo-N.

5.3.6 Results (CNH Canvases), next steps, recommendations (to replicate the solutions), feedback

- A lot of participants wanted to recreate previous activities from other stakeholders within their own territory while putting a focus on migrants
- There was a focus on educational projects, workshops with natural materials and the exchange of everyday knowledge such as cooking recipes and fairy tales between inhabitants and migrants.
- It is important to include migrants in existing structures and give them the opportunity to experience local culture, rather than segregating them in a new activity, which is not sustainably integrated in the existing framework of partners.
- Feedback on the CNH Canvas usefulness and fit in the local process and workshop>
- Participants struggled in the first place to grasp the meaning of all different fields (such as cost structure, needs, governance) and needed some intense introduction.
- Participants were unsure where to put their ideas, because they covered more than one field
- Participants understood, that for the action to succeed, all aspects of the canvas had to be recognized.

Table 20. INTO results. Prioritization of ideas to canvas by the core index. 1 Führungen und Bildungsprogramme, um insbesondere Migranten das Natur- und Kulturerbe der Region nahe zu bringen (Geo-N).

Savonia Business Model Canvas	
<p>Wichtige Partner Key partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Book Presentation • Erlebnisse • Kräuter-Pflanzen-Früchte, gestern und heute • Materialien entwickeln • MTB-Event • Visit of Summer Festival Lesvos 	<p>Schlüsselressourcen Key resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural Resource Geopark-School cooperation • Guided Tours (Ranger, Geopark-vor-Ort Gruppen) • Natural resource Geopark-MTB Training • Natural resource Geopark-Ranger activities • Flüchtlingstätter integrieren z.B. für Erfahrungsaustausch
<p>Führung Governance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange of activities with role models (Lesvos/Asti) • Overall concept • Overall concept • Project:coordination • Public relations • Sporevents 	<p>Bedürfnisse und Möglichkeiten Needs and Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infomedien für Zielgruppen, dass sie von unseren Angeboten erfahren z.B. in Kommunen verteilen
<p>Wert schaffen: Schlüsselaktivitäten Creating value: key activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fruit Variety of the year • Lesung mit Odo Odenwald • Mein Lieblingskuchen, Rezepte sammeln von Migranten und Odenwäldern + Backtage + testen • Neues Aktionsprogramm entwickeln • Unsere Kulturlandschaft 	<p>Wert schaffen: Nutznießer Creating value: beneficiaries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ausstellungsentwicklung (Sprachen) • Nordic-Walking im Felsenmeer, zusammen mit Freudenberg • Nordic-Walking-Trail • The day of orchard • Warum sind wir wie wir sind. Unser kulturelles Erbe am lokalen Beispiel Fischbachtal, Schloss + Museum • Workshop + Führungen mit Migranten im Rahmen des 10. Waldkunstpfades + der deutsch-syrischen Gesellschaft, Waldkunstpfad • - Austausch von Mythen, Sagen und Überlieferungen. Einheimische und Zugewanderte erzählen sich gegenseitig aus der Legendenwelt ihrer Kulturen
<p>Kostenstruktur Cost structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financing 	<p>Wert erfassen Capturing value</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wunsch: Wie kann man die Scheu überwinden in Kontakt zu treten?

Table 21. Into results. Prioritization of ideas by the core index. 2 Optionen schaffen, Zielgruppen jeden Alters die Teilnahme und die Erfahrung zu ermöglichen, mit Kunst im ländlichen Raum zu arbeiten (Geo-N)

Savonia Business Model Canvas	
<p style="text-align: center;">Beziehungen und Kanäle Relationships and channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neuen und alten Künstlerinnen und Künstlern eine Plattform bieten 	<p style="text-align: center;">Wichtige Partner Key partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Einladungs-App für sämtliche aktuelle und anstehende Aktivitäten • Global Nomadic Art Project • Landart training exchange, Geo-N/Geopark Lesvos
<p style="text-align: center;">Schlüsselressourcen Key resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural Resource Geopark-School cooperation • Erstellen Kochbuch • Natural resource Geopark-MTB Training • Natural resource Geopark-Ranger activities 	<p style="text-align: center;">Führung Governance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kontaktperson für Migranten schaffen • Bewerbungsverfahren
<p style="text-align: center;">Wert schaffen: Schlüsselaktivitäten Creating value: key activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bearbeitungskunst der Römer zu zeigen in ländlicher Umgebung • International Forest Art Trail • Self guided tour 	<p style="text-align: center;">Wert schaffen: Nutznießer Creating value: beneficiaries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kunstprojekt anlässlich 10. Waldkunstpfad gemeinsam mit Grube Messel • Infopunkte + Skulptureninfotafeln z.B. neuer BfH Messel, hier wohnen auch viele ausländische Studenten • Selbstwahrnehmung im Feisenmeer + am Feisenberg, was wir in natürlichen Formationen sehen bzw. interpretieren • Tanzen wie zu Hause, gegenseitig austauschen und miteinander bewegen

Table 22. INTO results. Prioritization of ideas to canvas by the core index. 3 Unterstützung von Training und Beschäftigung (Geo-N).

Savonia Business Model Canvas	
<p>Wichtige Partner Key partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ABC-Card Game (UNESCO World Heritage Messel Pit) • Bienenworkshop auf dem Gelände Internationales Waldkunst-Zentrum mit Jürgen Parg, Daniel Schaffner für Schulklassen (Waldkunstplatz) • Kurs: Kultur und Verstehen, Gemeinsam ein Team bilden • Gemeinsames Musizieren von regional typischen Weisen in der Natur (Migranten und heimisch), Bauen von Naturinstrumenten • Zusammenarbeit mit karitativen Einrichtungen 	<p>Schlüsselressourcen Key resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural Resource Geopark-School cooperation • Natural resource Geopark-ITB Training • Natural resource Geopark-Ranger activities • School Workshops
<p>Wert schaffen: Schlüsselaktivitäten Creating value: key activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental education with school classes (UNESCO World Heritage Site Messel Pit) • Geo-Naturpark-Bergstraße-Odenwald-Lesbos: Preparation of educational material for both territories • Internship with female migrants (International Forest Art) • Tierbeobachtung im Wald, einheimische Fauna erleben, beobachten, Tierspuren finden, zuordnen 	<p>Wert schaffen: Nutznießer Creating value: beneficiaries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Konzepte Integration • Arbeiten mit heimischen Steinmaterialien, künstlerisch, funktional • Welche Kompetenzen können Migranten vermitteln?
<p>Kostenstruktur Cost structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finanzierung 	<p>Wert erfassen Capturing value</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education for SDGs, Heft entwickeln b.z. Landschaft, Wissen, Nahrung, Klima, Risiken

5.4 Arts & Festivals (R4): Kulturno Izobrazevalno Drustvo KIBLA

5.4.1 Overall Description

Negova is a village in the hills in the west part of the municipality of Gornja Radgona, which is located at the north eastern part of Slovenia namely at the area of Ščavnica valley and at the wine-growing area of the Radgona hills. It borders neighbouring Austria along the Mura River and on the other borders with municipalities of Apače, Radenci, Sveti Jurij ob Ščavnici, Cerkvjenjak, Benedikt, Sveta Ana in Sveta Trojica v Slovenskih goricah. It measures 75 km² and is part of the Pomurska statistical region. The municipality of Gornja Radgona covers 30 settlements, where, according to the available data for 2016, a total of 8,471 persons live. The mean age of people in Gornja Radgona is 44 years, which is higher than the national average (42.6). The municipality is known for fairs, viticulture and Gornja Radgona sparkling wine.

The Negova Castle, where meetings will be hosted, has supposedly developed from the wooden shooting manor which was set here as early as the 11th or 12th century. It was first mentioned in 1425 as Vest Egaw. Negova Castle consists of three parts. The old castle originates from the 2nd half of the 14th century. The new castle, built in 1615 is the second part, and Pristava, which was used as an outbuilding, the third part. The total net floor area of all buildings is 4839.35 m². The Negova Castle area has been declared a cultural monument of national importance. Since 2014, the Negova Castle has been the domicile of the Photographic Federation of Slovenia which organises exhibitions of well-established Slovene and foreign masters of photography within the project "Fotograd". The Negova Castle encompasses a complex of buildings representing an architectural, tourist and business whole suitable for business meetings, educational activities, events and organisation of celebrations and weddings. The complex of buildings also includes a rich herbal park. The Manor House hosts a Tourist Information Centre. The surrounding area of Negova is rich with mineral springs – natural mineral water and ponds. The Negova Regional Park and the Negova Lake are protected as a regional park, and its surroundings are well known for their natural and cultural values.

5.4.2 Process description.

The process started at the end of May, 2019, in a business model training event at Crete, and ended in November, 2019. The process involved 3 video meetings with Savonia to design the context, participants, goals and organisation. Savonia also participated into the business model workshop, 27 of September at the Negova Castle. The workshop participants brainstormed 86 ideas which were evaluated by the INTO tool against four evaluation criteria. The results were given as a draft CNH Canvas.

5.4.3 Goal of the process

Kibla and Kultprotur set as goal to, firstly to draft four CNH Canvases, and, secondly, to elaborate one CNH Canvas in a business model process applying the INTO tool.

5.4.4 List of selected model actions for the BM process

Table 23. Model actions Kibla.

RM2-1	Improve services: eco-mobility, Wi-Fi connection, tourism services, signals, maps, radio...
RM8-1	Creation of a set of tourists packs, composed by FOOD related activities (i.e. the "Middle Age Menus"), ART (i.e. Middle Age poetry performance), NATURALISTIC Activities, etc.
RM4.10	Design a calendar of each fair of folk heritage and festivals and fairs to promote tourism.
RM7.7	Collaborate with other theatres, arts centres arts programmers in the area to provide a joined up cultural offer

5.4.5 Organisation of the workshop

The workshop was organised at Negova Castle and it gathered around 15 participants presenting different interest groups.

5.4.6 Results (CNH Canvases), next steps, recommendations (to replicate the solutions), feedback

Three CNH Canvases were drafted. Ideas to one CNH Canvas (RM 2-1) were brainstormed at the workshop, and the canvas was evaluated with the INTO tool after the workshop. 8 evaluators made the evaluation against the four criteria, environmental, social and economical sustainability and feasibility. The draft Canvas was made but the final result in English was not available for this report.

Table 24. RM 2-1. Improve services: eco-mobility, Wi-Fi connection, tourism services, signals, maps, radio...

INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		VALUE PROPOSITION	CREATING VALUE	
Key Resources Negova Castle	Key Partners Ministry of Culture, Gornja Radgona Municipality, stakeholders, local community, companies	Needs & Opportunities Social Value: involve local community and region and state into complementary activities of making the Castle as an extraordinary cultural asset. Economical Value: cultural heritage, touristic packages, handcrafts and applied art, local food and products, cultural and educational activities, investments in program and infrastructure. Environmental Value: attractive site and surrounding, natural park, beautiful landscape, lakes and water springs, bioenergy points, forests and meadows, Feasibility: cooperation between key partners and economical sector and development policies of the region, state and EU.	Key Activities - establish broadband Wi-Fi connection in the site - design eco tourist packages - promote eco-mobility - enhance public transport to urban centers - make a map of the area's interesting, special points, handicrafts, agrotourisms, restaurants, vacancies... - create applications for mobile devices	Beneficiaries employees - guests - tourists - villagers - area inhabitants - citizens and wider population (EU+)
Governance Kultprotur			Relationships & Channels - state (government, Ministry of Culture) - municipality (Gornja Radgona) - region (Štajerska) - cultural organisations and institutions - artists and artists associations - tourist organisations - partners - associations, networks and project consortiums - stakeholders	
Cost Structure Wi-Fi connection: 2.000 eur tourism services: 5.000 eur maps: 3.000 eur apps: 10.000 eur media; 5.000 eur eco-mobility: 5.000 eur			Capturing Value EU Ministry of Culture Municipality of Gornja Radgona Visitors Travelers Connoisseurs Artists Entrepreneurs Companies	
FINANCIAL MODEL /INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

Table 25. INTO results. Prioritization of ideas by core index. Prioritized CNH Canvas RM 2-1. 86 Ideas from the business model workshop and Table 10 were evaluated and prioritized by using core index. Evaluation was done in Slovenian language by 8 local evaluators.

Savonia Business Model Canvas	
<p>Ključni partnerji Key partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Novi investitorji / New investors • Javni interes / Public interest • Ponudniki storitev / Service providers • Gostince - hotelir / Caterer - hotelier 	<p>Odnosi in kanali Relationships and channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kolesarska mreža / Cycling Network • Slovenska kultura / Slovenian culture • Aktivnosti za otroke / Activities for children • EU dogodki in SLO gastronomija / EU events and SLO gastronomy • Pop-up dogodki, znanj kuharji / Pop-up events, famous chefs • Oglasevanje / Advertising • POTREBE IN PRILICNOSTI / NEEDS AND OPPORTUNITIES • Promocijski material / Promotional material • Spletna stran gradu Negova / Web site of castle Negova • Svetovalec za potovanje / Trip advisor • Uporaba WIFI povezave na gradu / Using WIFI connection at the castle
<p>Ključne aktivnosti key activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • narediti zemljevid zamimivih posebnih točk nočnih del agroturizmov restavracij promet • oblikovati eko turistične pakete • spodbujati eko mobilnost • okrepiti javni prevoz do mestnih središč 	<p>Upravljanje Governance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Izvajanje turističnih storitev / Providing tourist services • Obnova starega gradu / Renovation of the old castle • Izvajanje turističnih storitev / Providing tourist services
<p>Potrebe & priložnosti Value proposition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eksperimentiranja in kreativna "nova" lokalna hrana in ponudba vin / Experimental & creative "new" local food and wine offer • Zeliščni wellness center / Herbal wellness center • Okoljska vrednost: privlačna lokacija in okolica • Ponudbe poti z energetskimi točkami / Hiking trails with energy points • Sposoba električnih koles / Renting electric bikes • Družbena vrednost: vključiti lokalno skupnost in regijo ter državo v dopolnilne dejavnosti • Umetniška rezidenca / Artists residence • Doživljanje / Adventures • Dvig ekološke kulture zainteresirane javnosti / Raising ecological culture for the interested public • Gospodarska vrednost: kulturna dediščina • vključiti lokalno skupnost in regijo ter državo v dopolnilne dejavnosti • Izvedljivost: sodelovanje med ključnimi partnerji in gospodarstvom sektorjem in razvojnim politikami regije • Transport / Prevoz 	<p>Ključni viri Key resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU projekti / EU project
<p>Struktura stroškov Cost structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gostinska ponudba / Catering, culinary offer • Vzdrževanje gradu / Castle maintenance • Projekti, predstave / Projects, events • zaposlovanje: 3.000 eur • Stroški osebeja / Staff costs • ekološka mobilnost: 5.000 eur • aplikacije: 10.000 eur • mediji: 5.000 eur • Novi programi in projekti / New programs and project • turistične storitve: 5.000 eur • Stroški kačipotov / Cost of signpost • Prevoz / Transport • Zaposilivni stroški / Employment costs 	<p>Upravičenci beneficiaries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gošče • Wellness doživljanje v okolju / Wellness experience in the environment (fishing) ... • privlačni okolja • razvijani in širše prebivalstvo (EU +) • vasčani • Donatki proizvajalci hrane / Local food producers • Turisti
<p>Zajemna vrednost Capturing value</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU: 15.000 eur • Občina Gornje Radgonce: 5.000 eur • Wellness ponudba / Wellness offer • Poslovna ponudba na trgu / Business proposition for the market 	<p>Upravičenci beneficiaries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gošče • Wellness doživljanje v okolju / Wellness experience in the environment (fishing) ... • privlačni okolja • razvijani in širše prebivalstvo (EU +) • vasčani • Donatki proizvajalci hrane / Local food producers • Turisti

Figures 8-10. Business model workshop at the Negova Castle, Slovenia.

Table 26. Draft CNH Canvas on RM 7-7. Collaborate with other theatres, arts centres arts programmers in the area to provide a joined up cultural offer

INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		VALUE PROPOSITION	CREATING VALUE	
Key Resources Castle, site, area, surrounding	Key Partners Ministry of Culture, Gornja Radgona Municipality, stakeholders, local community, theatres, arts centers arts programmers in the area, international partners	Needs & Opportunities Needs: technical equipment, stages Opportunities: cultural destination, festival venue, artistic point, attractive program, guests, visitors, jobs - Social Value: involve local community and region and state into complementary activities of making the Castle as an extraordinary cultural asset.	Key Activities - initiate various pilot art programs - invite theatres, arts centres arts programmers from the area to collaborate - design special common programs for the castle - prepare spaces inside and outside to be venues - prepare art workshops and educational courses - make special art & heritage packages including local products and food - establish art & culture festivals - organise meetings, symposiums of art and culture professionals	Beneficiaries - employees - guests - tourists - villagers - area inhabitants - citizens and wider population (EU+)
Governance Kultprotur		Economical Value: cultural heritage, touristic packages, handcrafts and applied art, local food and products, cultural and educational activities, investments in program and infrastructure. Environmental Value: attractive site and surrounding, natural park, beautiful landscape, lakes and water springs, bioenergy points, forests and meadows, Feasibility: cooperation between key partners and economical sector and development policies of the region, state and EU. 70.000 EUR	Relationships & Channels - state (government, Ministry of Culture) - municipality (Gornja Radgona) - region (Štajerska) - cultural organisations and institutions - artists and artists associations - tourist organisations - partners - associations, networks and project consortiums - stakeholders	
Cost Structure Musical program: 15.000 eur Theatre program: 20.000 eur Visual arts program: 10.000 eur Audio-visual production: 5.000 eur Marketing and promotion: 5.000 eur Technical equipment: 10.000 eur Material costs: 5.000 eur		Capturing Value visible and attractive castle and area - appropriate infrastructure - indoor and outdoor venues - attractive events and festivals - workshops, symposiums, meetings - tradition - nature and landscape - unique historical settlement - peaceful location for artistic creation		
FINANCIAL MODEL /INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

Table 27. RM 8-1. Draft CNH Canvas on Creation of a set of tourists packs, composed by FOOD related activities (i.e. he "Middle Age Menus"), ART (i.e. Middle Age poetry performance), NATURALISTIC Activities, etc.

INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		VALUE PROPOSITION	CREATING VALUE	
Key Resources Castle, site, area, surrounding	Key Partners Ministry of Culture, Gornja Radgona Municipality, stakeholders, local community, farmers, local food producers, handicrafts	Needs & Opportunities Needs: Operational Permit, Restaurant utensils Opportunities: culinary destination, guests, visitors, culinary program, jobs	Key Activities - creating FOOD program - design special kitchen accessories - creating NATURE program - organise visits to attractive natural sights - prepare culinary and art workshops - make culinary packages - promote local food and food products - offer excellent local products in the castle shop - organise visits to local food- and winemakers and agrotourisms, handicrafts, best restaurants	Beneficiaries - employees - guests / tourists - villagers - area inhabitants - citizens and wider population (EU+)
Governance Kultprotur			Relationships & Channels state (government, Ministry of Culture) - municipality (Gornja Radgona) - region (Štajerska) - cultural organisations and institutions - artists and artists associations - tourist organisations - partners - associations, networks and project consortiums - stakeholders	
Cost Structure FOOD program: 10.000 eur NATURE program: 10.000 eur FOOD and NATURE festival: 10.000 eur Trainings and workshops: 5.000 eur Marketing and promotion: 5.000 eur Apps: 10.000 eur Restaurant utensils: 10.000 eur Material costs: 5.000 eur		Capturing Value - visible and attractive castle and variegated area - appropriate infrastructure - indoor and outdoor venues - attractive FOOD events - FOOD festivals using ingredients from the area - local chefs - workshops, symposiums, meetings - tradition - nature and landscape - unique historical settlement		
FINANCIAL MODEL /INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

5.5 Resilience (R5): Comune di Appignano del Tronto (CoApp)

RESILIENCE

A Little Community Fighting for Being More Resilient and Competitive

5.5.1 Overall Description

Appignano del Tronto is characterized by the presence of dip slope rolling hills and light blue anti-dip slope rocky badlands which represent two sides of the same coin. This natural landscape has been shaped by three torrential rivers, “Chifente”, “Pioppo” and “Volubile”, which create scenery whose beauty is invaluable. They represent an eternal fight between the hydrogeological fragility and the beauty of the landscape.

This territory has a rural vocation. By cultivating the land, farmers can get excellent cereals and grapes, high quality olive oils, PDO olives, organic vegetable and fruit thanks to the tempered climate of central Italy. The sweet slopes host ovine, bovine and caprine animals that grow up in the open air, eat organic food and breathe clean air.

There are no industrial areas nearby, but you can find small agricultural businesses (various mills, dairies, wine cellars, organic and typical bakeries) and craft firms (manufacturing industries producing ceramic, laces, bobbins, embroidered jewels, etc.) which benefit from their own experience and look forward using new technologies at the same time.

Furthermore, Appignano del Tronto is proud of an ancient culture of producing and setting up firework shows and a traditional music band, made up of different musician generations. In one of its main districts, whose name is “Valle Orta”, you can find a historical building complex, constructed by a local religious woman, Mother Maria Giacobetti. Nowadays this church is a place of pilgrimage and the building is used to host political refugees. The historical centre of the town, dating back to the Middle Ages, has been seriously damaged by the seismic crisis, which started on 24th August 2016.

At the moment, almost 50% of the houses in the historical heart of the town were condemned and traffic is partially interrupted. The priceless monumental churches were both badly damaged in its structure and decorations (frescos, paintings...) and so condemned. Local people are psychologically affected to these assets. They are worried about future conditions. Now it is fundamental to fix buildings, but it is also necessary to feel the sense of belonging to a community.

The HUB will be situated in a building belonging to the historic centre, in the north-west part of the town. This was a nursery school, partially renovated and subsequently converted into an auditorium. It represents a happy stage of the existence for local people. It means lightheartedness, friendship and education for them. It is a symbol of resilience, a place to set a basis to restart, even after a disaster. The facility has got a priceless cultural value in our grandparents, parents and sons’ minds.

5.5.2 Process description

The business model process started at the end of May in Crete with a first bilateral meeting with Savonia, and followed by two videomeetings to design the process, goals and methods according to the guideline. One CNH canvas was drafted before the workshop. Ideas both from the draft and the workshop were combined and added to the evaluation environment at Into.savonia.fi. Evaluation was made in two weeks after the workshop. Evaluation was quite comprehensive – 15 evaluators evaluated the ideas against four evaluation criteria. The results were analysed by using the portfolio analysis and as result CNH Canvas was given presenting the best ideas in a prioritized list in the CNH canvas.

5.5.3 Goal of the process

The goal was to elaborate one strategic CNH canvas, promoting business, social cohesion and resilience at the region.

5.5.4 List of selected model actions for the BM process

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5.5.5 Organisation of the workshop

The workshop was organised 14 of September, 2019 at Appignano del Tronto and having 14 participant from different interest groups: cultural associations, farms/companies, public-body, scientific partners, and other local participants.

Agenda of the meeting :

16h30m 1st Introduction: Ruritage State of the art: Antonella d'Angelo (CoApp)

16h45m 2nd Introduction: Ruritage State of the art at Appignano del Tronto + Business Model Workshop rules: Gianluca Vagnarelli PM (CoApp) and Tuomo Eskelinen (Savonia University)

17h15m Business Model Workshop 18h30m Evaluation of the actions through INTO-Tool

19h Final discussion and buffet

20h End of Business Model Workshop

Figures 11-13. Business model workshop at Appignano del Tronto.

5.5.6 Results (CNH Canvases), next steps, recommendations (to replicate the solutions), feedback

Table 28. Before the workshop drafted CNH Canvas at Appignano del Tronto

INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		VALUE PROPOSITION	CREATING VALUE	
<p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - cultural resources: medieval centre, historical churches, historical buildings, intangible heritage; - natural resources: calanchi (Badlands), rolling hills, Adriatic Sea, Appennini mountains; - other resources: local food, wine, local traditions and handicraft; - financial resources: European funds, regional funds, other public investments, foundations, business angels; - human resources: Ruritage staff, Ruritage Rule models, technical and scientific expertise, volunteers, member of local associations, local entrepreneurs; - infrastructure: Ancona airport, Ancona seaport, highway, public transport, local roads, Rural Heritage HUB; 	<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ruritage Rule models; - Ruritage Knowledge facilitator partners; - Ruritage stakeholders; - Private investors; - Banks and Foundations; - Local land owners; - Public bodies (Municipalities, Marche Region, GAL); - Local Associations (Pro loco - Frammenti-Oratorio); - University of Camerino, regional federation of geologists, INGV 	<p>Needs & Opportunities</p> <p><i>Cultural Value:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) to enhance and promoting existing tangible cultural attributes; 2) to rediscover Intangible Cultural aspects; 3) to strengthen local identity and awareness; 4) to establish international networks and contacts; 5) to strength awareness about natural disasters; <p><i>Economic values:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) to boost private investments; 2) to promote entrepreneurship skills and new businesses; 3) to support company internationalization; 4) to enhance Micro and SME competitiveness; 5) to generate new revenue; 6) to attract new tourists; <p><i>Social Value:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) to strength resilience; 2) to enhance social cohesion; 3) to improve social inclusion; 4) to reduce depopulation, poverty and unemployment; 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - training and equipment to improve community resilience; - Rural Heritage HUB events; - co-creation service-design methodology; - training activities; - incentives for increasing private investments in Appignano del Tronto; - heritage marketing and storytelling; 	<p>Beneficiaries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - citizens of Appignano del Tronto; - local companies; - local cultural associations; - tourists; - local products customers; - civil society; - agriturismo; - Ruritage stakeholders;
<p>Governance</p> <p>Model of governance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) scientific networking to improve community resilience; 2) Ethic path for developing social cohesion and inclusion; 3) association/foundation to boost private investments; 		<p><i>Environmental values:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) to create new nature walks; 2) to promote the typical landscape; 3) to promote new sustainable businesses; 4) to enhance sustainability as cross value; 5) to reduce the ecological footprint; 6) to support cruel free products; 	<p>Relationships & Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - communicate through storytelling approach; - communicate through "Ruritage – Appignano del Tronto" Facebook page; - communicate through Ruritage network (newsletter ecc.); - to target audiences: tourists, investors, customers; 	
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - personnel costs; - marketing costs; - governance cost; - training; - Rural Heritage HUB; 		<p>Capturing Value</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - a more safe and resilient community; investments; - new companies and entrepreneurs; - new sustainable and social responsible businesses; level of local identity awareness; - a more strong and cohesive community; level of Cultural Heritage protection and promotion; - an increased in the level of effective communication and marketing strategy; - new services and local products; 		
FINANCIAL MODEL /INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

Ideas from the participants were brainstormed at the workshop, after combining and analysing the ideas, a total of 148 ideas were added to INTO tool for multicriteria evaluation. 15 evaluators evaluated the ideas in two weeks after the workshop, resulting into 3186 evaluation grades. The evaluation was done in Italian language.

Figure 14: Result from idea brainstorming to CNH Canvas, Appignano del Tronto

Prioritization of the 148 ideas to CNH Canvas was made by using the core index. The final canvas will be done by using the prioritization and discussion.

Table 29. INTO results. Prioritization of 148 ideas by using the core index.

Savonia Business Model Canvas	
<p>relazioni e canali</p> <p>partner chiave</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aziende agricole locali • Centro Studi Francesco di Appignano • Comune di Appignano del Tronto • Stakeholders di Ruritage • Testimoni della Mezzadria • Unione Europea 	<p>risorse chiave</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • altre risorse • altre risorse 2 • risorse culturali • risorse culturali 2 • risorse naturali • risorse naturali 2 • risorse umane <p>proposta di valore</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • bellezza • Creare contatti e network internazionali (CV) • Patrimonio culturale tangibile (CV) • promuovere i Calanchi • promuovere il paesaggio tipico (EN V) • promuovere il senso di pace e tranquillità • promuovere la diversità del paesaggio • Promuovere le competenze imprenditoriali e nuove imprese (EV) • promuovere nuovi business sostenibili (EN V) • Rafforzare la resilienza (SV) • rigenerare l'ambiente naturale delle colline • riscoperta del patrimonio culturale intangibile <p>attività chiave</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • favorire un approccio sostenibile all'ambiente • formazione ed equipaggiamenti per rafforzare la resilienza della comunità • piattaforma digitale • promuovere i prodotti locali nei comuni e nelle attività commerciali limitrofe • supporto alle aziende locali • eventi nel rural heritage hub di Appignano Del Tronto • promozione e online marketing • rigenerare il paesaggio naturale <p>beneficiari</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • agriturismi • associazioni culturali • aziende agricole • bambini • stakeholder di Ruritage • turisti • clienti di produttori locali • scuole • giovani produttori locali • L'essere umano <p>valore di acquisizione</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • nuovi percorsi naturalistici • una comunicazione più efficace ed una strategia di marketing • una comunità locale più resiliente e più sicura • una maggiore conservazione e promozione del patrimonio culturale e naturale
<p>governance e gestione</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • comune e produttori locali 	<p>struttura dei costi</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • costi per la formazione

CNH canvas in English was not available for this report.

5.6 Landscape (R6): Integrated Management of Madra Geopark in Gediz-Bakircay Basins

5.6.1 Overall description

R6 is located on the Bakircay Basin of Izmir which is fertile agricultural basin has been home historically to many ancient civilizations including the world-famous historical heritage site of Pergamon. At the outskirts of this heritage site, there stands Asklepion, as a healing centre of the ancient world where natural treatments like sport, theatre and music were used for the first time. Project site covers Bergama, Dikili and Kınık district municipalities. The main source of income is agriculture. The region's agricultural products of particular fame are for instance the grapes and the pine nuts from the highlands of Kozak, but the region is also an olive producing area, one of the main agricultural outputs. The highlands offer spectacular forest and mountain tourism opportunities with a wide variety of Cultural and Natural Heritage sites.

Firstly, Izmir Metropolitan Municipality has recently completed Gediz-Bakircay Basins Local Development Strategy (2015-2016). The idea is to provide for local sustainable development with particular emphasis on natural and cultural assets of the region. The Municipality has decided to implement key actions of this strategy document as a model for local rural economic development in other districts under its jurisdiction. A geopark proposal in the north has been accepted and placed in 2030 regional master plan development report. The proposed Geopark site located on Madra Mountain, at the northern end of Izmir. This site has remarkable geological features like magmatic bodies (granite) and tor topography (see map). The surrounding area includes old mining works (ancient Pergamon gold mines).

Secondly, The region is rich with local food production but is weak in geographical certification and marketing. Important agricultural products are red-black grapes peculiar to the region, pine nuts, olives and local honey. The region and its natural endowments are seriously threatened by mining interests. Upgrading gastronomical dimension of the tourism services of regions are also needed rapidly. Several developments are particularly positive in this respect; Izmir's acceptance into the ECF's Eurovelo cycling tourism network, the newly planned sea line between Dikili and Lesvos will all contribute to the enhancement of this tourism networks. Another issue has been the declining incomes from pine fruit for the last several years, a major source of income in the villages. Several attempts have been made to diversify this income via alternative agricultural production and the Metropolitan Municipality has supported the rural population to diversify into honey production. This diversification will be augmented by the development of agro-forestry products by the planting of different species of locally known trees (liquorice) and berry bushes amenable to beekeeping, on the banks of the Gocbeyli Pond/ lakelet. The beekeeping has been providing additional income for the village.

Another issue that the only living master of the manufacture of Pergamum parchment maker also lives in

Bergama. Bergama is home to a lively cultural atmosphere with many festivals and happenings. Many local artisanal traditions are alive in Bergama, local food and agricultural produce festivals are plentiful. Bergama has a lively Roma population that keeps its musical tradition alive. Musical events around their typical musical style are organized. Plans to develop this music tradition through the formation of a local orchestra are in place. Some examples from the arts and crafts field in Bergama and environs can be seen below.

Finally, the physical location of the HUB is an old primary school building in the village Yukarıbey. This 'Village Living Hub' has been created via renovation of an old school building. Yukarıbey is also home to an active local tourism and local rural development society which will have an important role supporting RURITAGE. Included in the Izmir Metropolitan Municipality rural development plan for Gediz-Bakircay regions is the revival of the traditional "village hub" in a modern format, appropriately termed the "contemporary/modern village hub". These modern meeting places are envisaged to cover a large spectrum of cultural-economic-marketing activities in the region.

5.6.2 Process description

The Business Model Canvas widely used in the business world has been tailored to CNH by Savonia. It has been a very useful tool to think about the key elements of the potential or defined actions within the RURITAGE Project. The Metropolitan Municipality invited the stakeholders that can support and share their experiences with their businesses as well as to see how they can support the actions. The actions planned for the area can not be planned as a business as we know it. There are a number of social factors that need to be overcome within the area. In a business model the main idea is to make profit in order to ensure the continuity of the business. Although the sustainability of the actions is one of the key aspects of the businesses in the landscape, food and arts & festivals focus area for the Metropolitan Municipality is to find solutions to socio economic problems of the area while uncover the historical and natural potential of the area.

All the model actions/best practices (Del 1.1, TEC) identified in the Role Models have been narrowed by the project team to 24 actions. The pre-selected 24 Role Model actions have been discussed and evaluated within the Participatory Workshop.

The weakness and needs that are within the baseline study done by Cartif also matches with the actions chosen. The Business Model workshop was run within the city centre but not the RHH. Most of the stakeholders have already joined other workshops during the course of the project. Other stakeholders were also informed about the project and invited by phone calls.

1. Brief Presentation of RURITAGE project objectives at local level, role of stakeholders and benefits of participation have been done explaining what has been done so far.
2. The purpose and structure of the Business Model Canvas was explained to participants.
3. Presentation of the BM workshop aims and dynamics as part of heritage-led regeneration planning

Thanks to Savonia for all the support and guidance before and during the workshop.

5.6.3 Goal of the process

The main goal of the RURITAGE project is to have a regeneration strategy, action plan and demonstration activities in the end. Looking from the perspective of a Business Model Izmir team will be able to develop more self-sufficient projects that might need a boost from the public in the beginning but can generate revenue to cover the basic costs while increasing the income of the locals with new business opportunities, value added products and services that can be offered.

This process will support stakeholders to work for one integrated vision to ensure rural regeneration via cultural and natural heritage of the region. This process also feeds collaboration in strategy development and participation in business development.

5.6.4 List of selected model actions for the BM process

Two stage selection. First list is generated as a result of participatory works. Before the workshop, the R6 project team prioritize all role model actions depending on needs, challenges and potentials for regeneration of the area. 24 of 64 role model actions selected for assessment within the participatory workshop. As a result of participants' prioritization during the workshop, eight role model actions which are listed in Table 14, determined as best practices for the area.

Table 30: Actions that were selected during the Participatory Workshop of R6

RM action	SIA	Name of action
RM3-1	Food	Support local farmers and producers in innovation projects
RM3-3	Food	Definition of marketing and communication strategies for the products
RM3-5	Food	Promote the environmental sustainability of the agro-food production, packaging and selling
RM4-10	Food	Design a calendar of each fair of folk heritage and festivals to promote tourism
RM8-2	Arts&Festivals	Promote and support local traditional activities
RM8-4	Arts&Festivals	Enhance the narrative of the place and promote the discovering of the territory through history
RM12-1	Landscape	Promote joint actions (also through PPP) to enhance heritage resources and create an internationally recognized brand
RM13-3	Landscape	Local Economic and Community Plan developed for the region

Business model workshop actions are selected from this list by project team of R6. Due to the Landscape SIA has strong relation with food and arts & festivals SIAs in the case of R6, business model canvas are developed for three actions by participants for actions of food and arts & festivals SIAs which are also have significance for regeneration of the site (Table 15).

Table 31: Actions of Business Model Workshop of R6

RM3.3	RM8.2	RM8.4
Definition of marketing and communication strategies for the products	Promote and support local traditional activities	Enhance the narrative of the place and promote the discovering of the territory through history

5.6.5 Organisation of the workshop

The organisation of business model workshop consist of pre-work on business canvas of selected actions, invitation of related stakeholders, setting the workshop place and conducting workshop process which is mentioned under the title 6.6.2. The workshop is held in the city center of Metropolitan Area of Izmir due to broad participation request and accessibility options to the RHH in the Yukarıbey Village. Variety of participants, 40 in total, from universities, local municipalities, chambers of professional, private sector, associations and also foundations provided valuable outputs in terms of potential collaborations and business model.

Due to large proportion of stakeholder participation to workshop is confirmed, three different business model canvas of different actions are prepared to work on within the workshop. Three business model canvas of different actions are prepared before the business model workshop for supporting moderators to execute idea generation process for each components of the business canvas. Especially the filled key actors component of the canvas are used for identification of the participants who can collaborate for related actions which is also used for participant invitations. Experiences of stakeholders enriched the canvases during the workshop. Ideas that are generated under components of business model canvases are collected however evaluation of the ideas realized after the workshop by the participants.

Potential business models that are related with chosen actions (Table 4) are discussed within three separate tables. Each table had different action and at least 13 participants who are collaborated in filling components of the business model canvas. After each canvas is filled, a roll-up session is organized to discuss all developed business models and ideas are collected and added. Evaluation results are extracted from INTO tool of Savonia University Applied Science.

5.6.6 Results (CNH Canvases), next steps, recommendations (to replicate the solutions), feedback

A total of 47 participants participated in the business models workshop, representing 2 people from universities, 6 people from individual stakeholder, 5 people from local and regional government institutions, 1 person from public service provider companies, 9 people from associations and professional chambers, 18 people from metropolitan municipality, 3 people from DEM, and 3 people from IZTECH. In addition to our official stakeholders, different organizations working on the related topics were invited to the workshop. The number of participants was quite high. Therefore, the participants worked on 3 different canvases at 3 different tables. The participants were grouped according to the canvas subjects to be discussed. In this way, it is aimed to create an efficient discussion environment according to the fields of interest. There was a lot of discussion on all three tables. Many important ideas emerged for the implementation of the actions. Participants especially pointed out very important addresses for key partners and key resources. The canvas model was a very efficient way to enrich the content of the action and to discuss it in all its aspects. The INTO Tool was not used after the workshop to evaluate one CNH Canvas.

The diversity of the participants and their active participation in the activities enabled to obtain productive outputs from the workshop. The feedback of the participants was generally positive.

However, it was observed that the participants had low beliefs about whether the ideas developed would be implemented or not. This is undoubtedly a reflection of the failed participatory processes experienced outside the Ruritage Project. This situation puts pressure on the concretization and implementation of the ideas developed.

Three business model canvases are developed in relation with three model actions that are mentioned above. Developed canvases are given under Annex I. Cultural and agricultural assets of the region taken into account in terms of brand creation and definition of marketing and communication strategies for products of the region in the scope of RM3.3 "Identification of marketing and communication strategies for the products" business model canvas.

Besides agricultural production, local products and geographical indication, unique geological features of site bring landscape and food-oriented strategies forefront. Producer cooperatives and local entrepreneurs especially women of the region seen as key actors in this action. Key activities mainly focused on providing research-based solution development for fertile soils, food production to marketing processes of the products and livestock to pasture management. Marketing tools and researches on product and service development and production are the main areas that cost structures have to be developed. It is aimed that through improvement of agricultural and animal husbandry activities and protection and sustainability of cultural heritage, increase in income and welfare of local people would be ensured.

Figure 15: The workshop gathered 40 participants who brainstormed three action canvases in three separated tables.

Business model that is developed in the scope of RM8.2 “Promote and support local traditional activities” builds a relation between local products and touristic activities, especially for local foods. From this point, support in organic production and ensure quality management for the products are mentioned as needs of the site. To extension of crafts is connected with innovative design and contemporary art and object design. Apart from agricultural products, collection of the story of the traditions is mentioned as another important need to enable effective and more extensive promotion.

Inventory of features and cultural assets of rural settlements, risk mapping for cultural heritage, promotion of the site within the existing international congress and using photograph safari to increase the visibility of the settlements in the area are the some of the key activities to be realized in order to implementation of developed business model. To realize this promotion activities, local cooperatives, culture, art and education foundations, chambers of professionals, local represents of central governments and local municipalities are identified to realized such kind of activities. And last business model canvas is developed for RM8.4 ‘Enhance the narrative of the place and promote the discovering of the territory through history’ action. Ideas that are generated for identification of marketing and communication strategies for the products are evaluated within INTO tool of Savonia. Ideas that are generated during the business model workshop are prioritised by the participants after the workshop with using INTO tool of Savonia. As a result of this evaluation, tailored business model canvas is developed to identify marketing and communication strategies of the local products (Tables 16-).

Unique geological futures of the site and fertile agricultural lands are evaluated as main resources of the marketing and communication strategies of the region. Producer cooperatives are seen as main actor to realize this business development action. Universities are coming fore front also with their research support in strategy development so establishing a research center is evaluated as an important activity that will be implemented for realization of the action to achieve regeneration target of the rural settlements and communities. Establishment of an institutional structure that will ensure the organization of activities and assume responsibilities has significance to manage governance of the process.

Table 32. INTO results. Prioritization of ideas by core index. Tailored business model canvas for identification of marketing and communication strategies for the products.

Savonia Business Model Canvas	
<p>İletişim ve Kanallar Relationships and channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Yerel ve ulusal medya kanalları 2- Sosyal medya 3- Ulusal ve uluslararası festival ve fuarlar 4- Çalıştaylar atölyeler periyodik toplantılar 5- Uluslararası iş birlikleri iletişim ağı 	<p>Başlıca Ortaklar Key partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Üretici kooperatifler 2- Üniversiteler 3- Yerel yönetimler 8- Yerel halk 4- Yerel girişimciler (pansiyoncu ve işletmeci kadınları) 6- Ticaret odaları
<p>Başlıca Kaynaklar Key resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5- Jeolojik enderlik ve su varlığı 6- Kaliteli mineral toprak varlığı 7- Anlık 2- Tarımsal ürünler (pamuk domates zeytin üzüm ayçiçeği) 3- Yerel gıdalar (püritma küllü bergama köftesi bergama tulumu) 4- Mera varlığı ve hayvanlık 1- Çam fistiği 8- Şaraplık 	<p>Yönetim Governance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Faaliyetlerin düzenlenmesini sağlayacak ve sorumlulukları üstlenecek bir kurumsal yapı oluşturulması 2- Gelişmelerin denetlenmesi için geri bildirim mekanizmasının kurulması
<p>İhtiyaçlar ve fırsatlar Needs and opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4- Bergama pamuğu üretiminin ve işlenmesinin teşvik edilmesi 6- Mera varlığı ile sürdürülebilir hayvancılığın geliştirilme ihtiyacı olması 8- Anlıkta ilgili faaliyetlerin geliştirilme ihtiyacının olması 1- Bazı ürünler için coğrafi işaretlenimin olması 2- Uluslararası ve ulusal ölçekte tanıtım ile markalaşma gereksinimi 3- Ürünlerin verim dışılığına çözüm ihtiyacı olması 7- Üretim gider maliyetlerinin geliştirilme ihtiyacının olması 	<p>Başlıca Faaliyetler Key activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Araştırma merkezinin kurulması 4- Yerimli topraklarda tarımsal üretimin teşvik edilmesi ve sağlanması 6- Mera yönetimi birliğinin kurulması 7- Kooperatifçiye teşvik edilmesi ve kooperatiflerin desteklenmesi 8- Yerel halk için bilgilendirme ve eğitim faaliyetleri düzenlenmesi 9- Tanıtım amaçlı organizasyonların geliştirilmesiyle birlikte hikayeleştirme ve markalaştırma çalışmalarının yapılması 2- Ürün işleme ve tohumluk üretim tesislerinin kurulması 6- Artızenal faaliyetler ile yerel gıda arasındaki ilişkinin kurulması
<p>Yararlanıcılar beneficiaries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Yerel halk 2- Üreticiler 3- Yerel işletme sahipleri 4- Sivil toplum kuruluşları 5- Yerel yönetimler 7- Son tüketiciler (kentte yaşayan vatandaşlar turistler ziyaretçiler) 8- Doğal yaşam ve ekolojik denge 6- Üniversiteler ve enstitüler 	<p>Maliyet Yapısı Cost structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Pazarlama araştırma için maliyet yapısı geliştirilmesi 2- Ürün ve hizmetlerin geliştirilmesi ve üretimin sağlanmasına yönelik araştırmalar için maliyet yapısı geliştirilmesi
<p>Üretilen Değer Capturing value</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Kültürel mirasın korunması ve sürdürülebilirliğinin sağlanması 2- Yerel halkın gelir ve refah seviyesinin arttırılmasının sağlanması 4- Tarımsal ve hayvancılık faaliyetlerinin geliştirilmesi 3- İç göçün engellenerek geri dönüşün altında kalması sağlanarak üretimin katılmasının gerçekleştirilmesi 	

Table 33. Tailored business model canvas for identification of marketing and communication strategies for the products. Ideas are evaluated with INTO tool and prioritized with core index.

Key Resources	Key partners	Needs & opportunities	Key activities	Beneficiaries
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Unique features of site's geology 2. Presence of mineral soil 3. Beekeeping 4. Agricultural products of the localities (cotton, tomatoes, olives, grapes, sunflowers) 5. Local foods (çığırtma, küllür, bergama meatball, bergama cheese) 6. Pasture presence and livestock 7. Pine nuts 8. Winemaking 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Producer cooperatives 2. Universities 3. Local municipalities 4. Local entrepreneurs (especially women in home boarding) 5. Local people 6. Private sector, local entrepreneurs 7. Chambers of Commerce 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote of Bergama cotton production and processing 2. Improvement of pasture and herd breeding 3. Improvement of beekeeping activities 4. Presence of geographical indication for certain products 5. Promotion and branding on an international and national scale 6. Solutions to low productivity of products 7. Improvement in production costs 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establishment of a research center 2. Promoting and ensuring agricultural production in fertile soils 3. Establishment of pasture management association 4. Encouraging and supporting cooperatives 5. Organizing awareness rising and training activities for local people 6. Development of promotional organizations along with storytelling and branding activities. 7. Establishment of crop processing and seed production facilities 8. Establishing the relationship between artisanal activities and local food 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Local people 2. Producers 3. Local business owners 4. Non-governmental organizations 5. Local municipalities 6. Universities and institutes 7. End consumers (citizens, tourists, visitors) 8. Universities and institutes
Governance			Relationships & channels	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establishment of an institutional structure that will ensure the organization of activities and assume responsibility 2. Establishing a feedback mechanism for monitoring the developments 			<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Local and national media channels 2. Social media 3. National and international festivals and fairs 4. Workshops, workshops, periodic meetings 5. International cooperation, communication network 	
Cost structure		Capturing value		
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Developing cost structure for marketing tools 2. Development of cost structure for researches on product and service development and production 		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Protection and sustainability of cultural heritage 2. Increasing the income and welfare of local people 3. Improvement of agricultural and animal husbandry activities 4. Preventing internal migration and ensuring that the young population stays in the field to participate in production 		

Other business model canvases that are generated during the business model workshop are given in (Tables 32-33).

Table 34. Developed busines model canvas for RM8.2 action during the workshop of R6

Key Resources	Key partners	Needs & opportunities	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wine production - Parchment production - Carpets and Kozak rugs with local patterns - Wood carving (woodman culture) - Basketry - Local agriculture / livestock activities and ancient production knowledge (tomato production and drying, viticulture, long fiber cotton production, citrus production, cheese production, okra, sunflower, etc.) - Pine nuts production - Pine nuts halva 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local people - Fine Arts, Communication, Business, Graphics and Chemistry departments of universities - Türk Eğitim Vakfı (education foundation) - Ege Çağdaş Eğitim Vakfı (education foundation) - Bergama Village Cooperative - Kozak Tourism Cooperative - Bisuder - 6*6*6 Rota Çalışmaları Grubu - Tema İzmir - Ege Orman Vakfı - İzmir Dağcılık İl Temsilciliği - Atölye Deneme – Sanat ve Ekolojik Çalışmalar Derneği - Çekirdek İzmir Permakültür Kolektifi - Bergama Berlin Film Festivali Organizasyonu - İBŞB Sosyal Projeler Dairesi Başkanlığı - BERKSAV - Slow Food Hareketi - DEPO Bergama - Bergama Amatör Fotoğraf Sanatları Derneği - İlçe Millî Eğitim Müdürlükleri - Halk Eğitim Merkezi Müdürlükleri - Gençlik İl ve İlçe Müdürlükleri - İzmir Turist Rehberleri Odası - TÜRSAB İzmir Bölge Müdürlüğü - İZTAV (İzmir Turizm Tanıtma Vakfı) - EBSO (Ege Bölgesi Sanayi Odası) - BERTO (Bergama Ticaret Odası) - Herkes için Mimarlık Derneği - Kınık ve Bergama Organize Sanayi Bölgeleri 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agro-tourism within the scope of local agriculture and animal husbandry activities to experience, promotion, generation of products' story - Determination of land suitable for organic agriculture and revitalization, maintenance and training of organic / traditional / regional / nature friendly / ancient agriculture activities in these areas - Opening of organic-local agricultural products markets - Increasing organic wine production and introducing to market - Introducing traditional pine nuts halva within the scope of gastronomy tourism and finding innovative usage areas for pine nuts - Encouraging local people to use local agricultural products in touristic activities. - Arrangement of nature walks in natural heritage areas, determination of trails, establishment of scouting branches for children - Conservation of historical and traditional architectural pattern of settlements - List of subjects that can be documented and photo safari - Researching the history of parchment production, training about its production method, disseminating it and adding it to today's cultural heritage list - Establish international cooperation to promote local musical heritage - Transfer of local weaving patterns and techniques to contemporary object designs - presentation story of traditions - Extension of basket production, provision of natural raw materials, development of innovative basket designs - Introducing certain cultural heritage values with symbolic value of the region - infrastructure improvements for in case of increase in no. of visitors according to promotion - Establishment of an entrepreneurial ecosystem for local, traditional events - Identifying the cultural products and activities for branding - Establishing quality management for each product to have marketing value - Investigation of the effects of quarries, coal mining and thermal power plant which are thought to negatively affect local products such as pine nuts. 	
Governance		Key activities	Relationships & channels
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UNIVERSIAD Model - Integrated Basin Management Plan - Tourism Master Plan of the Bakircay Basin - Bakircay Culture – Art Agency - Establishment of networked business models for cultural heritage and assets of the region 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - social media - Benefiting from social media channels of international institutions such as UNESCO - local media channels (radio and newspapers) - multi-language web site - web site of İzmir Metropolitan Municipality - billboards of metro and railway of the city - influencers of social media - international organizations - activities of İZTAV (İzmir Tourism Promotion Foundation)
Cost structure		Beneficiaries	Capturing value
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National / international funding sources, project writing and management for grant programs - Performing a detailed business model feasibility with subheadings - Cultural funds of Ministry of Culture - Resources of Pergamon Organized Industrial Zone (transfer resources to local events) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Women, Young people, Children, Elderly, People of İzmir, Employees, Regional Craftsmen, Disabled 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rural Development, prevention of migration (especially youngsters), diversity in production, environmental awareness rising, academic knowledge generation, improvement of women's social position, improvement of the entrepreneurship ecosystem, protection of abstract / tangible cultural assets, ensuring asset- based development

Table 35. Developed business model canvas for RM8.4 action during the workshop of R6

Key Resources	Key partners	Needs & opportunities	Key activities		Beneficiaries
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Academic studies about the region - Myths of Bergama (Eyüp Eriş) - From the eyes of travelers, Pergamum (Ilhan PINAR) - Flora and fauna assets of the region - Coast Guard - Resources and persons for social movements related to Gold Mine and Allanoi - archaeological and recent history studies (Osman Bayatlı) - Memory of elderly population - craftsmen 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - University departments related to Folklore - Prof Dr Hayriye ÖZEN (Ekonomi University) - Ahmet YARAŞ (Allanoi) - Craftsmen - Ecology Association - Attalos Association founded by those who left Bergama in Athens - Asia Minor Research Center (Athens) - Local History Researcher UĞUROL BARLAS - Elderly population in the region 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compilation of stories about recent religious, social and commercial structures. - The potential of the elderly population in the region is important for telling the story of the region - Mythological stories related to the ancient period - Recording of stories about refugees wishing to move to Europe - Creating a museum on exchange (population movements especially in Dikili and Bergama) - Recording of relevant stories about the exchange period in the region. - stories about local traditional craft branches - stories of geothermal formations - Narratives about ecological social movements in the region. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Village visits and meetings can be held at Village Cafes. - Observation and information gathering studies in rural areas - Video shootings and interviews - Contribute to the promotion of local stories through the application of visualization techniques - Creating a museum on exchange (population movement between Turkish and other nationalities) 	<p>Relationships & channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social media - Social media influencers (Cem SEYMEN) - national and local press - Thematic web site 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tourism Agencies - Village Tourism Cooperatives - Local People - Transportation providers - Artisans and businesses in the region
<p>Governance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - design projects to realize key activities under the coordination of the unit to be established by Izmir Metropolitan Municipality (IZM) Participation with; universities, IZM, district municipalities, mukhtars, Bergama Chamber of Commerce, BERKSAV, Local Associations, Provincial and District Culture and Tourism Directorates, Bergama Museum, Presidency of Excavation, Public Education Centers, Emre Senan Design Foundation, Regional Tourism Cooperatives, Pergamon Lovers Tourism Association 					
<p>Cost structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - From the support and grants of organizations such as World Bank and Development Agency - IZM and district municipalities funds - Funds from Culture and Tourism Ministry - Tourism agencies 			<p>Capturing value</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nature conservation and environmental awareness - Develop the sense of belonging of the local people. - Contribute to the development of awareness about cultural heritage. - Improving the quality of life of local people. - Increase the income level of the region - Contribute to increasing the awareness of the region. 		

Figure 16. The workshop gathered about 40 participants who brainstormed three action canvases in three separate tables. INTO evaluation took place in 1-3 weeks after the workshop.

6. Feedback, lessons learnt

- Business model processes and workshop were organized successfully at all 6 Replicators, resulting into 17 draft CNH canvases, and 13 of them were evaluated with the INTO tool resulting into CNH Canvases where the ideas have been prioritized.
- All Replicators used the INTO tool to evaluate between 1-4 CNH Canvases. The evaluation criteria were the same in all evaluations: environmental, social, economical sustainability, and feasibility. These criteria were selected beforehand by taking the most crucial criteria for the Ruritage project and rural regeneration. The prioritization in the CNH canvases reflects the evaluations against the chosen criteria and thus produce value added on the rural regeneration.
- The evaluations of draft CNH canvases in all cases were done carefully by a total of 132 evaluators and 15925 individual evaluations on ideas against the selected criteria. Most workshops focused on the brainstorming of ideas, and the evaluations were done after the workshop, but also during the workshop (Norway).
- Both creation of ideas locally, and their evaluations is an important contribution from the local participants to the business model process. In one case (Austria) also the number of verbal evaluations was considerably high, which helps in the further development of the business models.
- Creation and finalization of CNH Canvases requires more time than was planned. Further work is needed to develop and complete the CNH Canvases.

Table 36. Summary on the CNH Canvas processes in 6 Replicators.

Replicator	Nr. of CNH Canvases drafted	Nr. of CNH Canvases evaluated/prioritized with INTO tool	Idea count	Nr. of evaluators	Nr. individual evaluations on ideas	Nr. of development comments on ideas
ARGE GEOPARK	4	4	27,39, 24, 30	13,12,8,12	1190,1684, 684,1320	28,46, 24,17
MAGMA GEOPARK	3	3	34,26,49	4,8,9	347,470,1364	0,12,7
GEO-N GEOPARK	3	3	32,17,18	12,12,12	1405,747,794	16,11,12
KULTPROTUR-KIBLA	3	1	86	8	1350	0
COAPP	1	1	148	15	3186	4
MADRA GEOPARK	3	1	54	7	1384	2
Total	17	13	584	132	15925	179

7. Conclusions

- The INTO tool was successfully used for the multicriteria evaluation of CNH canvases in all Replicators. It provided quantitative data on the process, such as idea lists, comments on ideas, numbers of evaluations on ideas, and core index, which was used to prioritize and select best ideas for each business model. Hundreds of ideas were brainstormed in the business model workshops. Multicriteria evaluation of the ideas was done with the INTO tool. The prioritization of ideas support the selection of ideas to the core business models.
- Local participants contribution was quite remarkable: 584 ideas were evaluated online by 132 evaluators with over 15000 multicriteria evaluations, showing great interest, commitment and participation.
- The prioritization in the CNH canvases reflects the evaluations against the chosen criteria: environmental, social, economical sustainability, and feasibility and thus produce value added in the context of rural regeneration.
- The CNH Canvas framework proved to be useful and successful tool to identify essential elements of business model on model actions which are aimed to be replicable solutions in the regions. Also the feedback from the Replicators was good.
- Further discussion and development and testing of the business models will be needed on the value proposition, needs and opportunities, key activities, key resources, financing model etc.. The work done, the CNH canvases and prioritization of ideas gives good starting point for further development. The business model process and workshops provided good opportunities for co-creation and learning.

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RURITAGE

Heritage for Rural Regeneration

Guidelines for the Business Models and Investment Strategy Local Workshop

For Rs

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Table 1: Abbreviations

BM	Business Model
BMC	Business Model Canvas
CNH	Cultural and Natural Heritage
INTO	INTO tool at into.savonia.fi
MCDS	Multi-criteria decision support
R	Replicator
RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RM	Role Model
SIA	Systemic Innovation Area

Objective

○ General Objective

Following the Participatory Workshop, the Business Models Workshop is the next stepping stone in the co-development of heritage-led regeneration strategies for Replicators. The task aims to develop replicable and up-scalable participative business models for the various actions to be implemented in the Replicators' territory that may be developed in a viable and sustainable way.

Using an innovative business model framework, stakeholders will be supported in developing tailored opportunities and initiatives within the six Replicators, with specific recommendations to replicate and tailor the actions identified in the Role Models.

Using the Business Canvas approach applied to CNH, this process is informed by the data gathering in the RURITAGE project, the Model Actions and the Lessons Learnt from the Role Models and from active engagement with the Replicators so that innovative business models and financial strategies can be defined for each scenario. The Canvas Business Models (Del 3.3) will then feed into the next related tasks - heritage-led regeneration plans, strategies and demonstration projects.

Approach

During RURITAGE the model actions/best practices (Del 1.1, TEC) identified in the Role Models, and discussed in the Participatory Workshop, forms the backdrop for the innovative business modelling process. Participating stakeholders have been identified during the first months of the project following specific guidelines developed by project partners (Del 2.1). The baseline study of the Replicators acts as a starting point (Del 1.4 CARTIF), whilst the Business Models are evaluated by establishing value-based criteria connected to Del. 4.1 (CARTIF).

To guide the business modelling process, the following supports are available:

- An innovative Business Model Canvas for CNH has been developed and pre-tested to support the first steps towards heritage-led regeneration plans, boosting co-creation, prioritising and co-ordination of actions. Further feedback will be collected to learn from the BM processes in each R.
- A detailed Guide is provided on how to use this Business Model Canvas to facilitate the strategy development.
- The Business Modelling process is complemented by the INTO tool – an online platform for making complex decision making faster and more efficient, involving different stakeholders and providing a transparent process. This tool is guided by Savonia, and is tailored to the situation of each Replicator.
- A training workshop was held for Replicators in Crete, along with face-to-face meetings with each Replicator, to explain the process involved and to demonstrate the use of the INTO Tool (into.savonia.fi) as a co-creation process to build actions on business models and investment strategy.
- Support will be provided to prepare for the Business Model Workshop to be held in each RHH.
- Further assistance, through a review and feedback process, will be provided with the tailored Business Model solutions for each Replicator that can be developed in a viable way from a financial and economic perspective.

The Business models process is guided by Savonia (leading task 3.2) and WestBIC, and supported by CE, CARTIF, UNIBO and ICLEI.

5 Steps Towards Business Models and Investment Strategy

The development process is a creative service design process including both divergent (Idea Development/ Model Actions) and convergent phases (evaluation and decision analysis produces prioritized list of actions). In the case of Business Modelling for Replicators in the RURITAGE project, the backdrop is the Model Actions selected from the Role Models that have potential for replication and tailoring for implementation in Replicator regions. This leads to the following 5 steps:

SAVONIA

CNH Canvas & model actions evaluation at the Replicator

4 Decision analysis with core value

Gives us a prioritized list of actions to support the BM and investment strategy creation. Results will be presented as a draft CNH Canvas, and as a prioritized list of actions with development comments and commitments (who will take lead for further actions)

Savonia Core Value calculation

Savonia Business Model Canvas

#	Scenarios	Idea name	Description
1	1771	Cooperation	Not active producer organisations should be brought into a Producer organisations should be cooperative with local gover
2	1771	Create a network of local farmers	Main farmers aware of the importance of making network 2
3	1771	Create children board	Set up board with local primary school children that will logg
4	1771	create public-private partnerships	create PPP
5	1771	Customer wants to see excellent views landscape	Customer wants to see excellent views and take photograph
6	1771	Statistics	Statistics

Discussion on results & Action plan BM and investment strategy

5

Expected results:

- 1) CNH Canvas
- 2) Prioritized and improved list of model actions

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Figures 1a and 1b. CNH Canvas creation and Evaluation of model actions with INTO tool. Business models and investment strategy process at Ruritage. Adapted from Kajanus et al. (2014⁴ and 2019⁵, Eskelinen et al., 2017⁶ and RURITAGE Project Plan.

Overview of the Steps

- Step 1 should already be completed as part of the Participatory Workshop, which includes a shortlisting for the proposed Model Actions, stakeholder identification and engagement
- Step 2 is the core Business Canvas completion as part of the workshop, which is organised according to the instruction in Section 3 and also using the Guide in Annex I.
- Using the online INTO tool, <https://into.savonia.fi> Steps 3.1 and 3.2 involves the evaluation of the Actions so that they can be agreed and prioritised, using a range of selected criteria. This is further explained at the end of Annex I Guide.
- Steps 4 & 5, involves decision analysis and discussion of the results as a prioritisation exercise with the input/feedback from the stakeholders at the workshop using the agreed evaluation criteria. Portfolio analysis occupies core index to calculate the results, and to put the Model Actions into a prioritized list (according to Kajanus et al., 2014). The results will be organised within the CNH Canvas framework.

⁴ Kajanus, Iire, Eskelinen, Heinonen, Hansen: Business model design: new tools for business systems innovation. Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research 08/2014; 29(6). DOI:10.1080/02827581.2014.949301.

⁵ Kajanus M, et al., What can we learn from business models in the European forest sector: Exploring the key elements of new business model designs Forest Policy and Economics. Volume 99, February 2019, Pages 145-156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2018.04.005>

⁶ Eskelinen, T., Räsänen, T., Santti, U., Happonen, A., & Kajanus, M. 2017. Designing a Business Model for Environmental Monitoring Services Using Fast MCDS Innovation Support Tools. Technology Innovation Management Review, 7(11): 36-46. <http://doi.org/10.22215/timreview/1119>

Timeline

The timeline for undertaking the Local Business Models Workshop is identified below, as part of the process of developing heritage-led regeneration plans.

Timeline and Project input

Figure 2: Timeline and Project Inputs for the development of Rural Regeneration Plans for RURITAGE Replicators

To facilitate this timeline, the Training Workshop for Rs on Business Models took place in Crete at the end of May, along with face-to-face discussions with Savonia to guide the process for the Local Business Model Workshops.

The guidance documents for organising and running the Workshop and the tools to be used are circulated in advance so that the business model workshops will be organized by every local Hub, guided by Savonia and WestBIC, with follow-up support to be provided according to the timeline above.

How to Organise the Workshop

○ Venue

Ideally, the venue for the event is the local Rural Heritage Hub. The venue should facilitate both plenary sessions with all participating stakeholders, as well as smaller groups (4-7 people each) at round-table workshops, to provide inputs to the Canvas Templates.

If the RHH has insufficient space, considering the estimated number of participating stakeholders and the workshop format, the organisers should identify another suitable venue in a location close-by.

○ Target Groups

Similar to the Participatory Workshop, all potential stakeholders at the Replicators, including:

- Policy: regional and local governing bodies, territorial development institutions, mgt of CNH sites, etc.
- Public: local residents, associations, schools, local action groups, civil society organizations, etc.
- Research: universities and research institutes, etc.
- Industry/services/investors: tourism industry representatives, key value chain representatives, centres for territorial development, foundations, transport, health and leisure providers, media, press, etc.

○ When to Engage Stakeholders?

Most stakeholders will already be engaged with the RHH at this stage, including for the previous Participatory Workshop. For the Local BM Workshop, it is recommended that invitations to the relevant stakeholders are issued well in advance (at least 15 days before the event), to maximise participation.

○ Proposed Agenda

4. Brief Presentation of RURITAGE project objectives at local level, role of stakeholders and benefits of participation (if new stakeholders are present).
5. Brief Summary of the Results of the Participatory Workshop, including selection of Model Actions
6. Presentation of the BM workshop aims and dynamics as part of heritage-led regeneration planning
7. Circulation of Templates and Guides to be used
8. Presentation of the draft Canvas completed for each Model Action (see 3.7 below)
9. Group work to review and complete the Canvas boxes, following the Templates and Guides provided
10. Plenary sessions to present the outputs and agree the results
11. Identification of any additional Actions emerging, and not already considered and complete similar process
12. Introduction of INTO tool for Evaluation of selected Actions and Decision Making on priorities
13. Circulation of BM Workshop Evaluation Questionnaire to Participants
14. Overview of next steps and Hub activities foreseen

Further information on the running of the Workshop is included in Section 3.8 overleaf.

○ Duration

A half-day session of 3-4 hours is recommended, according to the proposed Agenda, with a mid-session coffee-break. The actual duration will depend on the number of stakeholders participating, the number of Model Actions selected, the level of engagement and preparatory work already undertaken. However, a longer session is not advised due to potentially reducing the interest of participating stakeholders.

○ Preparation and Materials

In order to prepare for the Local BM Workshop, the R's are asked to:

- Understand the role of the BM Workshop as part of the rural regeneration planning process
- Complete the Participatory Workshop to pre-select Model Actions of relevance to the Replicator region.
- Familiarise with the Canvas Templates and the BM process by consulting the guidelines provided
- Familiarise with the INTO tool at <https://into.savonia.fi/about>

The Business Model Canvas template and the Guide to its completion are provided to be used during the workshop, and beforehand for draft canvas preparation, (see 3.7 below). These may also be circulated in advance to Stakeholders as part of the participation invitation, if this is convenient.

○ Before the Workshop – Preparing a Canvas Draft

To provide structure to the Workshop and to save time in the event itself, prior to the workshop the Rs should take the selected Model Actions from the Participatory Workshop and develop a draft BM Canvas for each selected Action (using their preferred Canvas Model) and instructed by the guide that is provided in Annex I. Savonia and WestBIC are available to provide feedback on the draft canvases that are prepared prior to the Local BM workshop.

The draft Canvases will then be presented to the Stakeholders at the BM Workshop for discussion and completion.

○ During the Workshop

The workshop will follow a participatory format, with plenary sessions and smaller group workshops using the Business Model Canvas Template and Guide provided. The aim of the workshop, the format and the agenda should be presented clearly at the beginning of the event.

According to the Agenda, after presenting the overall RURITAGE project and results of the Participatory Workshop and selected Role Model Actions in plenary session, the next step is to present the Business Model Canvas Template and Guide (Annex I) that will be used. These can best be explained by using the examples of the draft Business Model Canvases that are pre-prepared for the selected Model Actions by the Rs.

Then it is time to arrange the participating stakeholders into round-table discussion groups (e.g. 4-7 persons per group) so that the draft canvases can be discussed, the information can be evaluated and new suggestions provided to improve and complete the canvas according to the guide. As an interactive session, this can be done through the use of sticky-notes to be attached to the relevant boxes of each Canvas Template as part of the review and feedback process, so that it can be presented at a plenary session afterwards, using the template, flipcharts, etc. as aids in the process.

It is envisaged that each draft Canvas will take approx. 30 minutes to review/complete. It will also take a further 5-10 minutes for the plenary presentation of each Canvas and to get feedback from all participants. Depending on the numbers of participants, and also the number of Model Actions selected, it may be feasible for each group to contribute to each draft Canvas and provide specific inputs/feedback. If there are additional draft Canvases for discussion, to complete the workshop within the suggested time limit, it may be more appropriate to divide the draft Canvases into smaller lots across the discussion groups to review, improve and complete. The specific groups can present their completed Canvases and can get inputs from the other participants through the plenary feedback sessions.

Towards the end of the session, assuming successful Canvas completion for Model Actions, it could be discussed about whether there are any other relevant Actions worth considering for the region in the context of heritage-led rural regeneration. If new proposals emerge, then the Canvas preparation work can be undertaken (in groups or plenary) so that a draft may be prepared. This can then be discussed with UNIBO and CE, to discuss the potential and justification for including new Actions within the heritage-led regeneration planning.

The next Steps include the Evaluation, decision making and discussion using the online INTO tool, further explained at the end of Annex I.

At the end of the Workshop, participants should be invited to complete the Workshop Evaluation Questionnaire (Annex II).

○ After the Workshop

After the workshop, the draft Canvases should be updated and shared with Savonia and WestBIC for review and feedback so that they can be finalised and then used as part of the heritage-led regeneration planning and investment strategies.

The Replicator/Hub Co-ordinator also needs to complete the Business Model Workshop Event Report according to the Template provided in Annex III.

Expected Result

The Principal result of the process is a strategy for CNH business and investment presented in the CNH Canvas framework, focusing on the selected Model Actions. A business model canvas can be completed for each Model Action, using either the CNH or traditional Canvas depending on the Action selected. Each R is expected to have identified and prioritised a number of specific Actions they want to develop further. These can then be used for the further development of their regeneration plans.

Costs for Local Workshop

Costs relate to providing the workshop location/facilities and providing catering to participants. Assuming the use of the Rural Heritage Hub as the local workshop venue, the envisaged costs should then be approx. €500 - €1,000. In some cases, local sponsorship arrangements may be possible for some of the costs.

Tools and Materials

- The CNH Canvas Framework and guide to its use (Annex I)
- INTO Tool: <https://Into.savonia.fi/about> provides case examples, video and demos on the INTO tool
- Multi-media Projector for presentations, presenting the BM process, the pre-selected Model Actions and draft Canvas(s) that are prepared in advance
- Paper, pens, sticky-notes to assist the participative workshop format
- Flipcharts to present small-group activities in plenary sessions
- Attendance Sheet - for participant signatures
- Business Model Event Evaluation Questionnaire for Stakeholders (Annex II)
- Business Model Event Report – for Hub Co-ordinators (Annex III)

Dissemination

Partners shall refer to the Dissemination and Communication plan (Del. 7.1, ICLEI) for the dissemination of this activity. Similar to the Participatory Workshop, **additional suggestions** as provided as follows:

- **Before the event:** distribute flyers/invitations to stakeholders, place posters in key locations, and disseminate the event through social media channels and website. Issue press releases to relevant newspapers.
- **During the event:** place posters, roll-ups, flyers, leaflets and other communication material in visible locations. Potential for some 'live' dissemination of the event on social media, posted on the accounts of the partner organisation and by tagging the project accounts and using relevant hashtags, using short video/ audio interviews and group photos with participants.
- **After the event:** publish pictures, videos and news about your event on the project website, your own website and possibly stakeholder websites as well as on social media and other relevant channels. Issue press releases to relevant newspapers.

Monitoring of the activity

FOR PARTICIPANTS:

- Business Model Workshop Evaluation questionnaire (refer to template in Annex II)

FOR HUB COORDINATORS:

- Business Model Workshop Event Report, within 15 days (refer to template in Annex III)
- Completed Business Model Canvas for each Model Action

ANNEX I: The CNH Business Model Canvas Framework & Guide

What is a Business Model?

A 'Business Model' is a common phrase used to explain how the different elements of an 'enterprise' work together to deliver value to the end-user or customer. It describes the rationale of how an organisation creates, delivers, and captures value, in economic, social, cultural or other contexts. It also describes how 'profit' is made from this 'value proposition'.⁷

The term business model is used for a broad range of informal and formal descriptions to represent core aspects of a business, including purpose, business process, target customers, offerings, strategies, infrastructure, organizational structures, sourcing, trading practices, operational processes and policies including culture. Technological development, digitalization, changing consumer values and behaviour are examples of drivers changing business models in several industries.

What is a Business Model Canvas?

A 'Business Model Canvas' is simply a tool to capture a visual format of a Business, centred around the Value Proposition. The original Business Model Canvas, developed by Osterwalder and Pigneur⁸ and illustrated below, consists of 3 key elements:

- **Value proposition:** what the customer or end-user wants?
- **Value creation and delivery:** What is needed to create and deliver the value proposition (Key Partners, Activities, Resources, Customers, Channels, etc.)?
- **Value capture:** This includes an analysis of the proposed Cost Structure and the Revenue Streams, i.e. how much will it cost to deliver the value proposition and how to generate income from the product or service that is delivered?

Figure 3: The Original Business Model Canvas

⁷Magretta, J. (2002). "Why business models matter." *Harvard Business Review* 80(5): 86-92.

⁸Osterwalder, A., Y. Pigneur and C. Tucci (2005). "Clarifying Business Models: Origins, Present, and Future of the Concept." *Communications of the Association for Information Systems* 16(1).

The purpose and use of the original business model canvas is well documented. Some useful video links that clearly explain how to use this Business Model Canvas are given as follows:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IP0cUBWTgpY>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=g4E3fhybhGM>

<https://vimeo.com/89106474>

Business Model Canvas Design for Cultural and Natural Heritage

For RURITAGE Replicators, a specific Business Model Canvas Framework has been developed to capture the various aspects of Cultural and Natural Heritage situations. It is adapted from the original Business Model Canvas (BMC) and from other adaptations of the Canvas applied to related contexts, as an easy-to-use tool to help capture the visual ‘story’ or strategy for heritage-led regeneration initiatives. It learns from various adaptations of the original BMC including the triple-layered sustainable BMC approach by Joyce and Paquin⁹, as well as specific BMC applications to related scenarios, e.g. BMC for Nature Based Solutions¹⁰.

This CNH Business Model Canvas is illustrated overleaf, which is divided into 4 key parts as building blocks of the overall Business Model:

1. **Value Proposition:** The Value Proposition remains at the centre of the CNH Business Model. However, in the case of heritage-led regeneration the needs and opportunities can be expanded to consider not only economic propositions but also cultural, environmental and other aspects that may be addressed.
2. **Key Infrastructure and Resources:** A key consideration is the Infrastructure and Resources that can be applied to develop heritage-led rural regeneration and resultant value. Both CNH-specific resources that provide a USP as well as other generic resources are required, alongside mobilising the relevant Partners as the building blocks to generate value. Governance is also introduced, which is key to ensure a sustainable and long-term management approach.
3. **Value Creation:** To create value, the development and implementation of key activities is placed alongside the main beneficiaries that are targeted, given their interdependent nature in rural regeneration strategies. The interactions between them are captured within the important Relationships and Channels box.
4. **Financial Modelling/Investment Strategy:** The overall Financial Modelling/Investment Strategy is achieved through implementation of a suitable cost structure for both capital and operational aspects, along with capturing value through appropriate revenue modelling, mindful that direct revenue is not always the only measure of value to be considered. Other measures, including environmental, social and cultural value/returns may also be relevant considerations

These building blocks are further elaborated in the following pages, along with a full guide to its use. A blank CNH Canvas Template is also provided with this guide.

The Canvas may be used for capturing the overall strategic planning for regeneration of the territory, as well as undertaking a Canvas exercise for each identified Model Action selected.

Note: Replicators are free to use the CNH Business Model Canvas, or the original Business Model Canvas if they prefer this format for their local situation.

⁹ Joyce, Alexandre & Paquin, Raymond. (2016). The triple layered business model canvas: A tool to design more sustainable business models. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 135. 10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.06.067.

¹⁰ Siobhan McQuaid, Trinity College Dublin & Horizon Nua, A Guide to using the Nature-Based Solutions Business Model Canvas, April 2019

Figure 4: Business Model Canvas (with guide notes) for Cultural and Natural Heritage

2. INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		1. VALUE PROPOSITION	3. CREATING VALUE	
<p>Key Resources</p> <p>These are the list of key resources from which the value can be created. It includes both the unique CNH resources that gives the region its USP, as well as other relevant resources to be applied.</p> <p>Example CNH Resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural • Natural • Other <p>Other Relevant Resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial • Human • Infrastructure • Other 	<p>Key Partners</p> <p>The involvement of Key Partners is usually a prerequisite so that the region can mobilise the resources and work collaboratively to create value for beneficiaries. Examples include:</p> <p>Owners Stakeholders Community Local Authorities Government Chambers NGOs Universities Investors Industry Media Others</p>	<p>Needs & Opportunities</p> <p style="color: green;">The Starting point for the Canvas is here!</p> <p>The initial effort is to consider what needs and opportunities are of value to beneficiaries and the region that can support rural regeneration that can be delivered through key activities, products and services that may be developed. There is wide ranging potential of CNH that can foster rural regeneration, including offering:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic Value • Environmental Value • Cultural Value • Social/Societal Value <p>The needs and opportunities identified will be specific to the given territory, but may be inspired by Role Models from other regions. Examples might include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing sustainable solutions, services or products • Maximising tourism potential • Enhancing visitor experience • Promoting cultural diversity • Sustainable rural food production • Localised services • Social inclusion • Others 	<p>Key Activities</p> <p>These are the core actions in terms of deliver on the value proposition, addressing needs and capitalising on opportunities identified. Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scenario work • Strategic Planning; • Product/ Service development; • Testing, Piloting, Demos • Marketing/Promotion; • Training & Education • LCA analysis • Co-creation with end-users/customers • Others 	<p>Beneficiaries</p> <p>This is a wide definition to capture the various target customers and user groups (that may also include some key partners) for who value will be created and delivered Examples may include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customers • End users • Visitors • Partners • Stakeholders • Community • Civic Society • Others
<p>Governance</p> <p>It is good practice to adopt an effective governance model that captures the inter-dependence of the partners, and allows for efficient mgt and operation of CNH-led activities. Therefore the focus is typically on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisational Structure(s) • Engagement model(s) • Ownership model(s) 		<p style="text-align: center;">Relationships and Channels</p> <p>Methods of communication and engagement with user-groups, including marketing and promotion are critical to success and sustainability of initiatives. Items to consider, relevant to the local context include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement and co-operation • Inclusion issues • Communications • Awareness campaigns • Other marketing and promotion activities 		
<p style="text-align: center;">Cost Structure</p> <p>Both Capital costs and Operational costs relating to developing/delivering the activities are key considerations, both of which may require investment to achieve the potential identified. In some cases, specific cost reduction strategies may be possible to deliver a sustainable cost structure. Therefore consider the following here:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capital costs and sources of finance • Operational model/costs • Cost reduction potential – volunteers/donations, etc 		<p style="text-align: center;">Capturing Value</p> <p>Value capture may include the traditional economic focus of making money/profit from activities. In the context of CNH, there may also be other considerations of how stakeholders wish to evaluate the value that is created. Therefore a combination of the following may be considered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic – Revenues, grants/subsidies, investments, etc. • Social / Societal – Quality of Life enhancements, Inclusion, Integration, etc. • Environmental – Carbon reduction, recycling, resilience, protection and conservation • Others 		
<p>4. FINANCIAL MODEL / INVESTMENT STRATEGY</p>				

Use of the CNH Business Model Canvas

The Business Model Canvas for CNH is designed to be used as a tool to support the planning and implementation of Heritage-led regeneration in Replicator regions involved in the RURITAGE project. In particular, it has the following identified uses:

Strategic Planning: Focusing on the model actions selected by Rs in the participatory workshop as a starting point, The CNH Business Model Canvas is a useful first step for individuals or groups to plan the implementation of CNH projects and initiatives. It helps in considering all the basic building blocks to develop a successful long-term and sustainable project.

Stakeholder engagement: The CNH Business Model Canvas helps to identify partners or beneficiaries that may be interested in getting involved in the planning and implementation. It is a useful tool to present heritage-led regeneration proposals to stakeholders and to get partners acquainted with the key elements of the project methodology: Systemic Innovation Areas (SIAs), 6 Capitals, and Cross-cutting themes in the RURITAGE approach. It also:

- Provides participants with experiential opportunities to learn about model actions
- Creates opportunity to express diverse stakeholder perspectives and foster mutual understanding
- Creates a safe space for brainstorming new innovative projects.

Investment Strategies for CNH: The CNH Business Model Canvas addresses the core elements of the overall Business Case to be made in creating value, identifying the capital/investment costs, stakeholders/partners and revenue modelling scenarios. In this regard it is a useful tool as the first step in identifying how to finance the development of CNH and heritage-led regeneration proposals.

Taking an innovative approach, it may throw up creative solutions through the combination of various stakeholders and resources to deliver on the value propositions identified and how to reach the target beneficiaries. This is one of the next steps in the RURITAGE approach to heritage led-rural regeneration support for Replicators.

Communication tool: Deriving economic value from CNH is a relatively new concept for some, and may be difficult to explain to stakeholders without the use of easy-to-use and accepted tools. The CNH Business Model Canvas provides a relatively simple way of communicating what you want to do and why, who should be involved and how that can successfully happen. The Business Model Canvas is an approach that is becoming widely understood by people from many different backgrounds.

Guide to Using the CNH Business Model Canvas

The CNH Business Model Canvas is supported by this Guide, a facilitated Group Workshop for Replicators as part of the RURITAGE project and individual consultations with R's, including support for local Business Model Workshops to be undertaken in Rural Heritage Hubs in Replicator regions.

The implementation of the BMC takes into consideration the Good Practices and Lessons Learnt from Business Modelling and Investment Strategies of Role Models within the RURITAGE project. It also draws on the Stakeholder listing, Baseline data and KPIs identified for RURITAGE monitoring as a method of capturing and monitoring the results of the process.

1. The Value Proposition of CNH-Led Initiatives

The first section of the CNH Business Model Canvas to be considered is the Value Proposition, with a focus on the value that can be offered through addressing customer/end-user needs and also for delivering on the opportunities identified for targeted Beneficiaries.

INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		1.VALUE PROPOSITION	CREATING VALUE	
Key Resources	Key Partners	Needs & Opportunities e.g. Providing sustainable solutions, services or products Maximising Tourism potential Enhancing visitor experience Promoting cultural diversity Sustainable rural food production Localised services Social inclusion Others	Key Activities	Beneficiaries
Governance			Relationships and Channels	
Cost Structure		Capturing Value		
FINANCIAL MODEL / INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

Figure 5: CNH Business Model Canvas – Focus on Value Proposition

From the RURITAGE Role Model analysis, the types of value proposition can be quite wide ranging. In the case of CNH it is important to look beyond the obvious products and services that deliver value but to also consider other potential value that may be relevant as part of rural regeneration, including:

- Economic Value - address key economic challenges in the region
- Environmental Value - addressing environmental challenges
- Cultural Value – Enhancing and promoting existing cultural attributes
- Social/societal value – addressing key social challenges in the community

It is also important to consider if there are further direct, or sometimes indirect value propositions that can be developed through rural regeneration strategies. The list of model actions, along with propositions that are generated across stakeholders may also lead to trade-offs amongst proposals, which can be both positive and negative. This will require further discussion and agreement within the context of the overall Business Model Canvas to achieve the overall aims.

2. Infrastructure and Resources

The second part of the CNH Business Model Canvas to be completed concerns the Infrastructure and Resources from which value creation can be generated. This is divided into three parts on the left side of the Model:

- Key Resources
- Key Partners
- Governance

2.INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		VALUE PROPOSITION	CREATING VALUE	
Key Resources	Key Partners	Needs & Opportunities	Key Activities	Beneficiaries
CNH Resources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural • Natural • Other Other Resources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial • Human • Infrastructure • Other 	e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Owners • Stakeholders • Community • Local Authorities • Government • Chambers • NGOs • Universities • Investors • Industry • Media • Others 		Relationships and Channels	
Governance				
Cost Structure		Capturing Value		
FINANCIAL MODEL / INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

Figure 6: CNH Business Model Canvas – Focus on Infrastructure & Resources

Key Resources: From a CNH perspective, a unique relates to heritage-led regeneration resources concerning cultural and natural and built infrastructure that can form the basis for the specific Value Proposition and set it apart from other regions as a potential USP. This is combined with other relevant resources, including financial, human and physical that make up the overall resource scenario that can be integrated and applied towards value creation.

Key Partners: Despite having many CNH Resources, regions will not fully benefit from its potential without the involvement and participation of Key Partners. As the Stakeholder listing shows, the interested Partners can be wide ranging as depicted above. Of note, often partners in various regeneration projects can also be key beneficiaries from a value creation perspective, discussed later.

Governance: Given the interdependence between various partners and stakeholders and the relevant resources, there is a need to adopt a good governance model for the management and operation of the CNH-led activities. These can sometimes be complex with many different partners and beneficiaries and priorities involved, therefore it is useful to consider this at an early stage to maximise the potential for long term success.

3. Creating Value

The next part of the CNH Business Model Canvas relates to Value Creation - mobilising and organising key resources and developing actions to deliver on the value proposition, which encompasses the following:

- Key Activities
- Beneficiaries
- Relationships and Channels

INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		VALUE PROPOSITION	3. CREATING VALUE	
Key Resources	Key Partners	Needs & Opportunities	Key Activities e.g. Scenario work; Opportunity identification; Strategic planning Product/ Service development; Testing, Piloting, Demos Marketing/Promotion; Training & Education LCA analysis Co-creation with end-users/customers Others	Beneficiaries e.g. Customers End users Visitors Partners Stakeholders Community Civic Society Others
			Relationships and Channels Engagement and co-operation Inclusion Communications Awareness campaign	
Governance				
Cost Structure			Capturing Value	
FINANCIAL MODEL / INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

Figure 7: CNH Business Model Canvas – Focus on Creating Value

Key Activities: This is the core of the ‘action’ in terms of deciding how to deliver on the value proposition to address customer needs and capitalise on opportunities identified. Activities may be very focused in nature to deliver specific tasks, but may also be more strategic to develop long-term plans for implementation to address needs in a structured way. The list of Role Model Actions provides a useful starting point for consideration of suitable activities for Replicators.

Key Beneficiaries: The term **Key Beneficiaries** is used as a wide definition to broaden the understanding of who may be the target customers and user groups. In the case of CNH and regeneration there can be many interested and affected parties, including project partners/ stakeholders in some cases. The value proposition and proposed activities should be developed appropriately to meet their varying needs.

Relationships and Channels: The methods of communication and engagement with user-groups and beneficiaries is critical to the success and sustainability of any project. Awareness creation and inclusion are important at the outset whilst focused approaches may be required for specific audiences.

4. Financial Modelling and Investment Strategies

In the final part of the inter-related CNH BMC, the costs associated with the activities and value that can be derived from their delivery are evaluated, aimed at developing a sustainable (or profitable) model and drafting an investment strategy according to the objectives of the proposal being considered.

INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		VALUE PROPOSITION	CREATING VALUE	
Key Resources	Key Partners	Needs & Opportunities	Key Activities	Beneficiaries
Governance			Relationships and Channels	
Cost Structure Capital costs Operational model/costs Cost reduction potential – volunteers/donations, etc Other		Capturing Value Economic – Revenues, grants/subsidies, investments, etc. Social / Societal – QoL enhancements, inclusion, Integration, etc. Environmental – Carbon reduction, recycling, resilience, protection and conservation Other		
4.FINANCIAL MODEL / INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

Figure 8: CNH Business Model Canvas – Focus on Capturing Value

Capturing Value: In the original Business Model Canvas, Capturing Value normally describes how enterprises make money from their value proposition. In the case of CNH-led rural regeneration, a wider approach is often relevant, reflecting the varied nature of these activities.

In particular, for some types of regeneration initiatives, producing substantial direct revenues, at least at the outset, can be challenging. This can be the case where there is a predominant public or social good, or an environmental or cultural bias. If relevant, such criteria may be used as indicators of Value Capture themselves. In these cases, Model Actions identify other funding sources, including grants, subsidies, donations and other creative options.

Cost Structure: The lessons learnt from the business analysis of Model Actions identifies the need to consider financing solutions and funding for both the capital aspects as well as operational costs as a key part of the business model. Cost reduction strategies may also be relevant, including the consideration of partnership approaches, volunteerism and the methods of sustainable operations.

The combination of these factors will form the basis of the overall **Financial Modelling/Investment Strategy**, aimed at developing a sustainable model for the proposed action(s). This often requires innovative approaches to satisfy the needs of multiple stakeholders.

Multi-Criteria Evaluation of Proposed Actions with INTO Tool

Each Action will be evaluated according to the set criteria. In the fast-track evaluation as part of a workshop, an optimal number of evaluation criteria is around 3-5 and takes about 30-60 minutes to perform.

The evaluation criteria will be decided before the business model workshop and will be added to the INTO evaluation environment in local language.

Business models are frequently evaluated by criteria like business potential, competitive advantage, sustainability, feasibility, and potential for economical impact or potential to attract investors. In Ruritage, our goal is that the actions would increase cultural, natural, built, social human and financial capital.

Figure 9. Community capitals by Butler Flora, 2008.

The following criteria are recommended:

Environmental value: Does the action promote environmental sustainability and limit the use on non-renewable resources? 1 not at all, 7 very much

Social value: e.g. Does the action promote social sustainability, transparency, wellbeing, equity, community engagement?, 1 = very little, 7, very much

Economical value: does the action bring potential for sustainable economical impact? Does the action boost new economies? : 1 not at all, 7 very much.

Feasibility: Is the action feasible in short-medium term, 3-5 yrs? Are the resources needed (in terms of knowledge, economic, human capital) available for the implementation? 1 not at all.. 7 very feasible

Idea	(Evaluated 1 / 53)	ENVIRONMENTAL VALUE (1 - 7) : Does the action promote environmental sustainability and limit the use on non-	SOCIAL VALUE (1 - 7) e.g. Does the action promote social sustainability, transparency, wellbeing, equity,	ECONOMICAL VALUE (1 - 7) does the action bring potential for sustainable economical impact? Does the action boost	FEASIBILITY (1 - 7) Is the action feasible in short-medium term, 3-5 yrs? Are the resources needed (in terms of	Comments
Evaluate - DEMO STRATEGIC CNH CANVAS WITH INTO TOOL Info						
The evaluation page expires on 8/10/2019 3:21:09 PM						
Ideas are evaluated against four value-based evaluation criteria:						
Environmental value: Does the action promote environmental sustainability and limit the use on non-renewable resources? 1 not at all, 7 very much						
Social value: e.g. Does the action promote social sustainability, transparency, wellbeing, equity, community engagement?, 1 = very little, 7, very much						
Economical value: does the action bring potential for sustainable economical impact? Does the action boost new economies? : 1 not at all, 7 very much.						
Feasibility: Is the action feasible in short-medium term, 3-5 yrs? Are the resources needed (in terms of knowledge, economic, human capital) available for the implementation? 1 not at all.. 7 very feasible						
Relationships and channels (7 ideas)						
Social media		(2.4)	(NaV)	(5.9)	(5.4)	OUR COMPANY IS EAGER TO DEVELOP A NEW SOCIAL MEDIA APP TO PROMOTE CULTURAL HERITAGE TOURISM IN OUR REGION
Meeting with the landowner		(NaV)	(NaV)	(NaV)	(NaV)	

Figure 10. INTO -evaluation environment can be tested at a demo process CNH CANVAS at: <https://into.savonia.fi/cnh-canvas/Evaluate> Key: Rur2019

Annex II: Business model event evaluation questionnaire

Objective

As part of the monitoring procedures in terms of efficacy and efficiency of Hub activities, a qualitative assessment will be made after each event asking for stakeholders' feedback on several aspects.

Indications

1. Translate the following questionnaire into your **local language** (or in English if considered)
2. Distribute the questionnaire either in **paper format** and/or through an **online form (Google form, Microsoft forms, etc)** or both. In case of paper format, make sure that these are placed in a visible place (e.g. in a stand or table nearby the entrance, next to the registration list). If in online format, make sure you send out the link to all participants and that you specify the deadline to fill it out.
3. During the event, take a few minutes to explain **why** this data is being collected and **how** participants should fill out the questionnaire.
4. You should at least collect **10-15 answers**.
5. After the event, complete the online survey placed on your event folder with the participant's answers OR upload answers **in English** in the SharePoint (Excel), within 15 days.

BUSINESS MODEL EVENT QUESTIONNAIRE				
<u>I. OVERALL EVALUATION</u>	<i>Please mark your answer</i>			
	VERY MUCH	MUCH	FAIR	INSUFFICIENT NOT AT ALL
How satisfied are you of the event organised?				
To what extent do you feel confident with the general aims of the project?				
To what extent do you consider this project relevant for your territory?				
To what extent do you consider relevant your involvement in the development or strengthening of the innovative strategies for promotion of cultural and natural heritage in your area?				
<u>II. DETAILED EVALUATION</u>	EXCELLENT VERY SATISFIED	GOOD SATISFIED	FAIR QUITE SATISFIED	INSUFFICIENT NOT SATISFIED
1. PRE-EVENT ORGANISATION				
Did you receive the invitation in good time?				
Did the invitation offer a clear picture of what the event was about?				
<i>If not through invitation, how did you learn about the event? Please specify</i>				
2. OBJECTIVES				
Do you have a clear picture of the purpose of the Business Model Canvas?				
Do you have a clear picture on the business models and investment strategy process?				
Do you have a clear picture of the purpose of the INTO tool?				
How well did the evaluation criteria fit to your business models process?				
How well did the event correspond to your expectations?				
3. HOW WOULD YOU RATE THE FOLLOWING?				
Business model Canvas usefulness				
INTO tool usefulness				
Quality of presentations – speakers (if any)				
Documentation & Visual aid				

Quality of moderation and of the Hub team				
Structure and overall design of the event				
Level of interaction among participants				
4. LOGISTICAL ASPECTS				
On-site organisation and support				
Venue's facility (Hub)				
Did the venue offer an environment that supports creativity?				
5. COMMENTS				
1. What did you most appreciate during the event?				
2. Do you have any recommendation for the improvement of the organization of the next Hub activities?				
3. After this event, are you interested in participating in future events?				

ANNEX III: Business models event report - Hub Co-ordinators

[Name of the organisation in charge of the event]

Venue	
Date	
Duration	
Type and number of stakeholders involved and role in the event	Please include the name of the different stakeholders involved and also the different SIAs they represent, if applicable i.e. local government 3 local food company 2 university etc.
Total number of participants	
Number of female participants (indicative)	
Number of male participants (indicative)	
Number of disabled people, if applicable	
Number of migrants, if applicable	

Agenda of the event

Please include the agenda of the event.

Photos of the event

Please provide some pictures from the event (making sure you comply with GDPR regulations)

Event assessment

Overall how would you rate the success of this specific event? (*mark only one option*)

- Very successful
- Fairly successful
- Not too successful
- Not successful at all

Please briefly describe the event including:

Your key takeaways from the BM workshop

Max. half page

Feedback on the CNH Canvas. How useful was it? How well did it fit in your local process and workshop?

Max. half page

A qualitative assessment will be made after each event asking for stakeholders' feedback on several aspects, with questionnaire format included in Annex II.

